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Proceeding summarizes the latest research presented at the 2025 International Scientific Conference, focusing on the synergy between classical mathematical theory and modern information technologies. The publication provides an in-depth examination of fundamental problems in the stability of dynamic systems, methods for solving differential equations, and innovative neural network architectures. Considerable attention is devoted to applied aspects, particularly the use of artificial intelligence of the critical infrastructure, robotics, cybersecurity, and smart agriculture. The authors propose effective algorithms and models for addressing complex tasks in monitoring, control, and decision-making under uncertainty.

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У збірнику підсумовано останні дослідження, представлені на Міжнародній науковій конференції 2025 року, зосереджені на синергії між класичною математичною теорією та сучасними інформаційними технологіями. Запропоновано поглиблений розгляд фундаментальних проблем стійкості динамічних систем, методів розв'язання диференціальних рівнянь та інноваційних архітектур нейронних мереж. Значна увага приділяється прикладним аспектам, зокрема використанню штучного інтелекту критичної інфраструктури, робототехніки, кібербезпеки та розумного сільського господарства. Авторами запропоновано ефективні алгоритми та моделі для вирішення складних завдань моніторингу, управління та прийняття рішень в умовах невизначеності.

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Article 1: Coordinate Free Method for the Identification of the Plane Curves and its Applications to Motion Planning

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Abstract: In this paper we present a method for representing a continuous curve in the plane by a function defined on a unit interval, which we call the angular characteristic function of the curve. This representation is invariant under translations, rotations and universal scaling and is well suited for curve shape recognition. We have used this function for feature extraction in an experimental system for optical recognition of handwritten characters and the approach, briefly described in this paper, has shown good results. For graphic primitives - circular arcs and line segments - the angular characteristic function representing them has a particularly simple form. This circumstance allows using the angular characteristic function in motion planning problems and in robotics. As an example of such applications, we present an algorithm that can be used in a system for automatic program generation for a robotic manipulator used for a cutting process. This is an algorithm for approximating a smooth curve in the plane by a sequence of such graphic primitives forming a continuous smooth curve (in which each segment is conjugate to its neighbors).

Conclusions: The suggested approach for recognizing plane curves was created with the intention of being utilized in tasks involving the recognition of handwritten characters. The core concept behind this method for identifying flat curves involves employing a unique function to discern the shape of a simple, continuous curve devoid of any self-intersections. Our primary focus was on character recognition techniques that involve the transformation of character images into a planar graph. This planar graph, generated through the conversion process, contains all the essential information required for recognition. As an outcome of our efforts, we designed software to put these algorithms into practice and applied it to conduct experiments involving the recognition of decimal digits in actual photographs. Due to the radical difference between the proposed method and the existing ones, the software was created as proof of concept solely to confirm the operability of the method. For the experiments, images of the symbols of the digits 1, 2, 3, 5 were used (numbers for which the planar graphs corresponding to their symbols do not contain cycles were used) generated in a relatively small number of instances (from 10 to 20 for each symbol) by the participant of the experiment. Based on this sample, a small database was created that allowed character recognition. Then, an experiment was conducted to recognize characters generated by the same participant in the experiment. In the course of several similar experiments, 100% recognition accuracy was observed (no recognition errors). We

emphasize that such experiments on small samples cannot be used for comparison with other methods and are only suitable as proof of concept.

Article 2: Point Control for Nonlocal in Time Model of Heat and Mass Transfer

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Abstract: We analyze an optimal control problem for a linear parabolic equation featuring a nonlocal-in-time integral term, which models heat and mass transfer processes influenced by past system states. These models play a vital role in a variety of areas, including but not limited to: high-performance computing, cancer treatment, additive manufacturing processes, etc. The focus is on pointwise control, implemented through a specific operator on the right-hand side of the equation. To address the optimal control problem, we employ a regularized formulation and provide different properties of both of the optimal control problems. Finally, we provide numerical simulations that illustrate the effectiveness of this approach in approximating optimal control solutions.

Conclusions: This paper develops a mathematical framework for modeling heat and mass transfer processes with memory effects, represented by a linear parabolic integro-differential equation incorporating a nonlocal in time integral term. The optimal control problem is formulated using a pointwise control strategy, which is particularly relevant for practical applications requiring precise localized influence. The main novelty lies in proving the existence of optimal control in the spaces considered for the investigated problem. To demonstrate the process of determining the optimal control, a computational example is provided. To solve the control problem, a regularized formulation is introduced, guaranteeing the existence of solutions and their convergence as the regularization parameter tends to zero. The Fréchet derivative of the cost functional is computed, enabling the use of a gradient-based optimization algorithm to determine optimal control numerical solutions. Computational experiments demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach. The findings indicate that the iterative optimization method successfully reduces the cost functional, yielding optimal control solutions that closely correspond to the desired system trajectory. Although only one example is included in the paper, the authors again emphasize the importance of initialization and step size selection on optimization performance. From an applied perspective, this research contributes to the advancement of efficient control methodologies for heat and mass transfer systems. The proposed framework has potential applications in a variety of areas: sustainable development (energy-efficient building management, industrial process optimization, and climate-responsive urban planning, etc.), high-performance computing, cancer treatment,

additive manufacturing processes, etc. Future directions may include modeling the case with more points of control (s □1), refining optimization techniques through adaptive step-size strategies, extending the model to capture nonlinear effects for broader real-world applicability, investigating controllability properties or/and asymptotic controllability, etc.

Article 3: Method of Representing of Indicator of Functional Stability of Distributed Information Systems in Time of Working in Autonomous Mode

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Abstract: Distributed information systems is very important instrument of solving different practical tasks. We may see it in different fields like medicine, banking and many other. But its active usage purposes a solving different other problems, related with its modeling and exploitation. Especially, it’s important in case, when information systems work in autonomous mode. This work purpose a method of description of dynamics of considered information system in time of working in autonomous mode.

Conclusions: The work purposes a method, how to describe a functional stability of distributed information system on time of working in autonomous mode. In one hand, this method may have a number important aspects like high difficulty or a number of additional tasks, but, in other hand, this method may be considered as a generalization of existing methods of estimation of functional stability, what allows to estimate it only in discrete moments of time. Described method may have many perspectives in usage in many fields like management [17], monitoring [18, 19] and many other [20, 21]. 4. References

Article 4: Spline-Based Solution of Nonlinear Periodic Boundary Value Problems for the Lienard Equation with Switching

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Abstract: This paper presents an iterative scheme for finding a solution to a nonlinear periodic boundary value problem for the Lienard equation with switching and its convergence conditions using the spline method and the Newton-Kantorovich method. We also study the problem of constructing a periodic solution for a model of a non-isothermal chemical reaction with switching, which is an example of the use of splines to solve a nonlinear periodic boundary value problem.

Conclusions: In conclusion, we note that proposed in the paper scheme for finding a solution of a nonlinear periodic boundary value problem for the Lienard equation with switches can be transferred to nonlinear boundary value problems for functional differential equations with switches [11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

Article 5: Functionally Stability Software-Hardware Neural Network “Neurocomputer”

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Abstract: This study presents a multilayer artificial neural network (ANN) that exhibits resilience to the failure of individual neurons. The architecture allows for disabling several neurons in hidden layers without a significant deterioration in prediction accuracy. To optimize the training process, we apply the Adam algorithm, mini-batch gradient descent, and regularization via dropout. We demonstrate that these techniques contribute to the creation of a functionally robust network representation, enabling the system to remain operational even in the presence of partial node failures. Theoretical findings are supported by experimental validation.

Conclusions: We proposed a method for enhancing the robustness of neural networks to neuron deactivation. We showed that using dropout and the Adam optimizer during training enables the network to maintain prediction accuracy even with up to 15% neuron loss. Both theoretical analysis and experimental validation confirm that the model remains stable and accurate under such conditions. Compared to previous work, our method aligns with modern trends in machine learning while offering a novel approach to architectural resilience. These findings are applicable to critical domains such as autonomous systems, diagnostics, and financial modeling. In summary: •Neural networks are not critically dependent on individual neurons. •Deactivation does not disrupt training gradients. •Larger networks are inherently more robust. •This is an architectural property, not a side effect of dropout. •Neuron

deactivation is a viable diagnostic and optimization tool. Our results confirm theoretical findings about network redundancy and offer a new perspective on functional robustness. Future work may explore adaptive reconfiguration of network topology in response to failure. Thus, functional robustness is an intrinsic property of neural networks.

Article 6: Exploring Neural Network Methods for Software of Military Object Detection in UAV Images

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Abstract: This paper is dedicated to the study and comparison of military object detection and classification methods in video streams obtained from unmanned aerial vehicles. The main objective is to identify the most effective approach based on predefined quality assessment criteria, particularly for identifying military objects, for further use in software development. Three detection and classification methods, namely Faster R-CNN, SSD, and YOLO, were used for the study. Three quality criteria for detection and classification methods were developed and described. An algorithm was proposed to determine the required number of images for calculating metrics with a predefined error ε . It was determined that for calculating a metric with an error on the order of 10^{-5} , 250 images are sufficient in the context of the task at hand. For each detection and classification method, corresponding metrics were calculated with the given error, followed by a comparative analysis of these methods based on the three metrics. During the comparative analysis, none of the methods demonstrated the highest results across all three quality criteria. Therefore, priorities were assigned to each metric based on the specific nature of the task. After analyzing the qualitative metrics of each detection and classification method and considering the chosen priorities, it was concluded that the most effective approach for identifying military objects in UAV video streams is the method based on the YOLO model.

Conclusions: After conducting a comparative analysis of the studied methods, it is difficult to definitively determine which one is the best for detecting and classifying military targets captured by UAVs, as none of the methods demonstrated the best results across all three quality criteria. In other words: 1. The Faster R-CNN-based method predicts the location of military targets most accurately (best for the IoU metric). 2. The YOLO-based method identifies military targets the fastest (best for the T metric). 3. There is no clear difference in terms of detection and classification capability between Faster R-CNN and YOLO, as both perform equally well. However, when looking at the numbers, YOLO shows slightly better results than Faster R-CNN in the R quality criterion. This advantage, though, is minimal (only 1.6%) and could be considered within the margin of calculation error. As observed from the results, the SSD-based

method did not outperform in any of the three quality criteria, so it is not considered a viable candidate for the future implementation of a military target detection and classification system for UAV video streams. Thus, a more detailed analysis of the results for the Faster R-CNN and YOLO methods is necessary to determine the most relevant method based on the computed quality criteria. Since neither method showed the best results across all three criteria, the next step is to prioritize each quality criterion. This will allow for a selection based on the context of the task to be solved using these methods. The R quality criterion, which evaluates the ability of the method to detect and classify military targets, is the most important and should be given the highest priority. This is because methods with a higher R value are capable of detecting more camouflaged military targets, such as people in military uniforms blending with the environment. This is particularly important in the context of territory monitoring and control using drones. The T quality criterion, which characterizes the speed of the method, should be given second priority because the methods will operate not with static images, but with real-time video streams from drones. To process and analyze all frames from the video stream in time, high-speed performance is essential. If the speed is insufficient, frames that may contain military targets will be skipped, resulting in missed detections. Therefore, the IoU quality criterion, which assesses the accuracy of object localization, takes third priority, as it is important for evaluating placement accuracy, but it does not carry as much weight as the ability to identify and classify objects. Based on the established priorities, the most relevant method for the given context will be determined. According to the R quality criterion, which holds the highest priority, the Faster R-CNN and YOLO methods showed nearly identical results, making it impossible to determine a clear winner at this point. Moving to the T metric, which has the second priority, the clear winner is the YOLO based method, as it is almost three times faster than the Faster R-CNN-based method based on the obtained results. Considering the final priority criterion, IoU, it was noted that Faster R-CNN performed 4.5% better than YOLO, but this advantage is minimal and not significant, as the IoU criterion holds the lowest priority. Therefore, given that the YOLO-based method was nearly three times faster than the Faster R-CNN-based method, the YOLO-based method was selected for the further development of the military target detection and classification system in UAV video streams.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 7: Cost-Sensitive Decision Trees with Prospect Theory for Churn Prediction

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Abstract: Customer churn significantly affects the profitability and sustainability of online retail businesses, requiring accurate prediction models for effective retention strategies. This paper presents a novel approach integrating machine learning (ML) methods and Cumulative Prospect Theory (CPT) to enhance churn prediction accuracy and economic efficiency. We developed a cost-sensitive Decision Tree classifier explicitly incorporating customer lifetime value (CLV) and promotional intervention costs. The model effectively identifies customer segments most responsive to retention interventions using extensive customer transaction data, engagement metrics, and satisfaction scores. The evaluation demonstrated that targeting customers with high CLV and moderate-to-high churn probabilities substantially improved financial outcomes. This integrated approach reduced unnecessary interventions and optimized resource allocation based on economic utility. The paper underscores the significance of combining behavioral economics and predictive analytics, recommending further exploring Bayesian and reinforcement learning methods for enhanced churn modeling.

Conclusions: This study explored the application of a cost-sensitive Decision Tree model integrated with utility based economic metrics for predicting customer churn in an online retail setting. By incorporating Customer Lifetime Value (CLV), intervention costs, and behavioral principles from Cumulative Prospect Theory (CPT), the model provided not only predictive insights but also actionable, economically rational strategies for customer retention. The results demonstrated that while the model's predictive accuracy was moderate, its value lay in its ability to distinguish between economically beneficial and non-beneficial interventions. The model successfully identified high-CLV customers with elevated churn risk, enabling targeted retention strategies that maximize return on investment (ROI). Feature engineering and utility-driven modeling revealed the importance of behavioral engagement indicators and historical transaction data in churn prediction. These findings support the hypothesis that enhancing machine learning models with utility-based frameworks leads to more effective and financially sound decision-making processes. The work contributes to the growing literature on economic-aware machine learning by providing a practical approach that balances predictive performance with financial impact. Future work should expand upon this foundation by integrating more dynamic customer behavior data, exploring alternative model architectures such as ensemble or reinforcement learning methods, and scaling the framework across different industry contexts. Ultimately, this research provides a strategic direction for businesses seeking to transform churn management from a reactive task into a predictive, profit-driven strategy.

Declaration on Generative AI During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly to check the grammar and spelling. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the publication's content.

Article 8: A Data-Driven Method for Software-Based Predicting the Risk of Fusarium Head Blight in Maize

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Abstract: Nowadays, the world agricultural practice of open-field crop production necessitates the development and implementation of intelligent methods and hardware and software solutions of information technologies that allow the implementation of a strategy for predictive management of agrotechnical processes. In this study, the scientific and applied problem of substantiating approaches to increasing the stress resistance of cereals has been solved by developing a computerized method for predicting the occurrence of Fusarium Head Blight based on software analysis of soil and climatic monitoring data. The practical implementation of the method is a computer Simulink model of intelligent analysis of soil and climatic data for predicting the probability of Fusarium Head Blight in maize for the agroclimatic conditions of the northern steppe and forest-steppe of Ukraine. The results of the computer experiment proved the effectiveness of the proposed computerized method in predicting the probability of Fusarium Head Blight in maize: the mean absolute error is 0.29%, the standard deviation varies from $\pm 6.02\%$ to $\pm 10.41\%$, and the coefficient of determination ranges from 0.65 to 0.91. The promising development of the developed method involves its integration into serial microcontroller devices with further testing in real agroclimatic operating conditions.

Conclusions: In this paper, a new approach to predicting the risk of Fusarium Head Blight in maize has been proposed and investigated based on the intelligent analysis of soil and climatic data obtained in the agroclimatic conditions of the northern steppe and forest-steppe of Ukraine. The application of the regression model resulted in an effective assessment of the probability of Fusarium Head Blight disease occurrence. The average absolute prediction error for the two agroclimatic zones is $0.29 \pm 8.22\%$, and the average determination coefficient is 0.78, which demonstrates the high predictive accuracy of the developed method for detecting Fusarium head blight of maize at the pre-symptomatic stage, which has been implemented as a computer model in Matlab & Simulink. The main advantages of the method include the possibility of early prediction of maize diseases, which will allow farmers to make timely decisions on plant protection by performing appropriate agricultural procedures. Further research will focus on the software integration of the proposed model into microcontroller devices of intelligent information technologies using fog computing techniques to conduct tests in real-world conditions.

Article 9: Planning of the Air Situation and the Location of Radar Equipment on the Electronic Map

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Abstract: This article presents an approach to planning and managing the air situation using an electronic map, with a focus on the optimal placement of radar equipment and real-time target tracking. The primary objective is to develop a software system that enables interactive modeling of the air environment, precise positioning of radar systems based on geographical coordinates, calculation of radar coverage areas, and detection of airborne targets. A mathematical model of radar coverage is proposed, along with algorithms for determining intersections between target trajectories and radar control zones. The study also explores methods for optimizing radar deployment to maximize coverage and minimize blind spots. Special emphasis is placed on data visualization techniques that enhance situational awareness, support decision-making, and streamline air defense operations. The developed approach is applicable in various domains, including military defense, airspace monitoring, and aviation security. It is particularly suitable for simulating combat scenarios, training radar operators, and developing decision support systems for both military and civilian use. The proposed solutions contribute to improving the efficiency of radar-based surveillance systems and optimizing airspace control strategies.

Conclusions: This article presents a comprehensive approach to planning the air situation and optimizing the deployment of radar systems (RLS), taking into account spatial coverage, airborne target movement, and integration with geographic information systems. To achieve these objectives, a set of mathematical models and algorithms was developed for calculating radar coverage areas based on geographic coordinates, detecting aerial objects with up to 100-meter precision, and constructing movement trajectories with intersection tracking. The implemented system demonstrated high performance in simulation scenarios involving multiple radar stations and moving targets. The results confirm the feasibility of applying the proposed methods for visualizing and planning radar deployments on digital maps. The system dynamically adapts to changes such as target movement or radar status (active, inactive, maintenance). A user friendly interface has also been implemented to support real-time interaction with the air situation. Among the system's limitations are the dependency on coverage point density and the quality of input geospatial data, which may affect the accuracy of trajectory modeling and detection verification. Promising directions for future research include the integration of terrain elevation models, weather condition data, and real-time sensor inputs (e.g., live radar feeds or UAV telemetry). In addition, it is advisable to explore advanced optimization strategies that prioritize defense objectives, overlapping radar fields, and likely threat vectors. The proposed system lays

the groundwork for the development of a fully functional decision support suite for air surveillance and defense planning. The experimental validation of the system confirmed its operational reliability and effectiveness. By aligning radar detection data with target trajectories stored in a NoSQL database and performing Haversine-based distance calculations, the system ensured accurate spatial correlation. Test scenarios with multiple radar systems underscored the importance of precise radar positioning, while simulation of radar relocation scenarios (e.g., NASAMS) demonstrated the critical need for strategic planning in maintaining full airspace coverage. Overall, the proposed solution provides a robust technological and analytical foundation for supporting air defense operations in complex and dynamic environments.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 10: Mathematical Model of Plant Diseases Classifier for Smart Agriculture Implemented on Small-Edge Devices

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Abstract: The development of digital agriculture opens up incredible potential for the implementation and provision of both care and crop control at all stages of plant growth. It should be noted that to ensure successful classification approaches, disease recognition tasks require the creation of a large dataset and large computing power for training. In particular, even creating a database of digital images of the same plant disease, but at different stages of its development (sprout, flowering, fruiting) is a laborious task. The authors proposed a modified approach to the classifier based on the support vector method, which will provide significant results without spending a lot of time on dataset preparation and economically using computational resources due to the short training time.

Conclusions: The authors analyzed existing solutions for plant health monitoring and present an affordable, multimodal approach that leverages stationary sensors and visual data to optimize agricultural. Obtained classifier for diagnosing plant diseases based on binary relevance approach the which consists of SVM’s, needs small dataset and short time for training model. This approach will allow the classifier to be fully adapted to the needs of a particular area or farm. In the future, the authors plan to expand the approach to classifying not only diseases, but also predicting the possibility of their occurrence based on temperature, humidity, and soil parameters.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 11: Modeling Threat in Cyberspace with Markov Processes

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Abstract: Markov processes are a powerful mathematical tool for analyzing and modeling threats in cybersecurity. This paper examines the application of discrete and continuous Markov processes for risk assessment, attack prediction, and optimization of defense strategies in cyberspace. A method for simulating attack dynamics based on Markov chains is proposed, along with the use of stochastic operators to evaluate the effectiveness of cybersecurity measures.

Conclusions: Markov processes are a powerful tool for analyzing cybersecurity threats. The use of discrete and continuous Markov models allows for improved attack prediction and optimization of defense strategies. Simulation approaches provide an effective way to assess risks and test cybersecurity policies before their implementation. This dynamic approach offers a powerful way to predict likely attack scenarios and can be extended for further analysis. The program code can be adapted for DDoS attacks by simulating multiple simultaneous attackers who randomly select nodes to attack, introducing a variable for each node that indicates its load level (e.g., the number of attacks). The simulation can be applied to modeling botnets (each attacker receives a list of target nodes and attacks them according to a certain pattern).

Declaration on Generative AI During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used X-GPT-4 and Gramby in order to: Grammar and spelling check. After using these tool(s)/service(s), the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the publication's content.

Article 12: Model for Food Supply Chain Stability Under Climate Variability with Semi-Markov Processes

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Abstract: Climate changes increasingly and significantly impact food supply chain stability, necessitating robust analytical frameworks for mitigating disruptions and optimizing resilience strategies. To accurately model and analyze the dynamics under stochastic climate conditions, we develop a system of linear difference equations determined by semi-Markov process. The approach captures dependencies in supply chain transitions. The moment equations are utilized to establish the conditions required

for ensuring food supply chain stability. As a case study, the model is implemented to analyze the food supply chain's stability under given weather conditions. The findings contribute to supply chain risk management by offering how Markov based modelling can be efficiently used to predict system stability, assess climate-induced disruptions, and enhance resilience strategies for food delivery overall.

Conclusions: In this study, by formulating moment equations, we quantified the behavior of the food supply chain system and investigated its stability under stochastic environmental conditions, such as moderate, tropical, and arid climate zones, modelled by semi-Markov process with jumps. This approach enabled us to assess the resilience of food distribution network by capturing transition intensities and delays influenced by climate-driven disruptions. The proposed methodology provides a versatile tool for analyzing a wide range of supply chains, in particular, stability. Moreover, the study lays the groundwork for future research on deriving explicit conditions for ergodicity, analyzing transient dynamics, integrating economic factors that may influence food supply chains, and developing sophisticated models for enhanced system analysis.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 13: A Computer Vision Approach for Detection of Asteroids Comets in Space Satellite Images

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Abstract: Numerous satellites orbit Earth, continuously capturing vast astronomical datasets that demand efficient, autonomous processing for timely analysis. In this work, we introduce a computer vision-based method tailored to detect moving objects in NEOSat imagery automatically—the data source of a Canadian space telescope dedicated to discovering comets and asteroids in our solar system. Our method reliably identifies objects with brightness differences from the background as low as 2% and robustly estimates their trajectories, whether linear or curved, even when the detectable path is as short as 10 pixels. Moreover, by integrating a dual-stage processing pipeline that incorporates both per-frame and composite-image evaluations,

the algorithm effectively reduces false positives while maintaining computational efficiency on standard laptop hardware. This scalable solution not only accelerates the discovery process but also enhances near-Earth object surveillance, providing a powerful tool for automated astronomical data analysis.

Conclusions: In this paper, we present an algorithm for detecting astronomical moving objects—such as comets and asteroids—in NEOSSat images provided by the Canadian Space Agency through their OpenData portal. The method begins by preprocessing the raw image data to mitigate sensor noise and systematic errors. Next, a combination of image processing and computer vision techniques—including spatial domain analysis, line segment detection (LSD), and morphological operations—is applied to extract and link the trajectories of moving targets. In the final stage, potential false positives are filtered out based on the presumption of consistent motion across consecutive frames, thereby isolating the true moving object paths. Our approach has demonstrated remarkable robustness, as it successfully detects targets with intensities as low as 2% above background brightness. It is also capable of identifying very short line streaks - down to 10 pixels - and reconstructing non-linear trajectories by estimating them from sequential linear segments. The complete solution can be executed on standard personal computers. **Conclusions keys:** **Robust Performance:** The technique reliably detects moving objects even under adverse conditions, such as low contrast and high background noise. This highlights the strength of combining advanced preprocessing with the inherent sensitivity of the LSD algorithm and morphological filtering. **Versatility:** By accommodating both linear and non-linear trajectories, the method proves adaptable for tracking a variety of astronomical objects, enhancing its utility for both automated surveillance and scientific discovery. **Accessibility:** The open-source release of the code and its intuitive interface democratizes access to sophisticated image processing tools, allowing researchers and citizen scientists to apply the method to NEOSSat data and potentially other astronomical datasets. **Future Directions:** The promising performance of this approach opens avenues for further development, such as integrating machine learning classifiers to further reduce false detections and extending the framework to analyze larger datasets or accommodate multiple moving objects simultaneously. Overall, the work offers a scalable, efficient, and practical solution for the continuous monitoring of near-Earth objects, contributing to both space situational awareness and the broader field of astronomical imaging.

Article 14: Approximation Scheme of Systems with Delay and Their Stability

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Abstract: This paper presents a framework for analyzing the exponential stability of linear differential equations with delay. To prove the proposed approach, an approximation scheme is used in which delay differential systems are replaced by a sequence of specially constructed ordinary differential equation (ODE) systems. The relationship between the solutions of the original delay system and its approximating ODE systems is thoroughly investigated. It is shown that, for a sufficiently large approximation dimension, the exponential stability of the original system with delay is equivalent to the exponential stability of its corresponding approximating ODE system. The roots of the characteristic equations associated with these ODE approximations closely match the non-asymptotic roots of the quasi-polynomials arising in linear difference equations with delay. By computing these roots and analyzing their distribution in the complex plane, conclusions about the stability or instability of the original system with delay can be drawn. A model example of a third-order linear delay system is presented. Two distinct stability regions with a correlation to the delay parameter are identified, within which the system remains exponentially stable. The obtained bounds refine those derived using the generalized D-decomposition method.

Conclusions: The purpose of this work is to apply approximation schemes for linear delay differential systems using a sequence of specially constructed ordinary differential equation (ODE) systems in order to analyze the stability of linear delay-difference equations. The stability analysis of linear systems with delay is reduced to verifying whether all roots of the corresponding quasi-polynomials have negative real parts. The study establishes that for a sufficiently high-dimensional approximating ODE system, this verification can be replaced by analyzing the location of the roots of the corresponding characteristic polynomials. The roots are computed using the NumPy library in the Python programming language. For a model example involving a third-order linear delay system, explicit formulas for the coefficients of the characteristic polynomial of the approximating ODE system are derived. Based on numerical simulations, two regions of the delay parameter were identified within which the system is exponentially stable. The obtained bounds refine the estimates produced using the generalized D decomposition method presented in [16].

Article 15: Analysis of News Messages Using the Sentiment Analysis Method

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Abstract: The increasing volume of news posts on social media highlights the need for analyzing their emotional tone to identify the authors' sentiments and their influence on the audience. The emotional component of news significantly impacts public opinion and behavior. The aim of this research is to develop a tool that automates the process of identifying specific trends and the emotional content of texts, thereby

improving the quality of public sentiment analysis and decision-making in the media sector. The study is based on modern machine learning and text analysis techniques. Data is collected using scraping tools, normalized through tokenization and lemmatization, and grouped by topic. Sentiment analysis is conducted using machine learning methods. The research resulted in the creation of a tool that automatically identifies positive, negative, or neutral emotions in news posts. Applying the tool provided accurate analytical and graphical reports, enabling the assessment of emotional distribution and trends in texts. The evaluation of the results demonstrated the tool's effectiveness and accuracy on real-world data. The obtained insights can be used to analyze public sentiments and predict their development. The developed tool for analyzing the emotional content of news posts on social media allows processing large volumes of textual information. It can also be employed by analytical companies, media monitoring agencies, and research institutions to detect manipulations, disinformation, and analyze their impact on public opinion.

Conclusions: The proposed solution provides users with a simple way to quickly and automatically collect large data sets, determine the required number of groups, and divide the data set into appropriate categories. Due to the use of low-complexity algorithms, the required running time is minimal, as well as the use of fairly low computer resources [15]. This article considered algorithms that are already widely used and have proven their effectiveness. The proposed system can also be run without an Internet connection by transferring pre-collected data sets to it, which makes it possible to use the solution in a completely offline mode.

Declaration on Generative AI The author(s) have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 16: Green Operator of a Linear Noetherian Boundary Value Problem for a Matrix Differential-Algebraic Equation

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Abstract: The solvability conditions and the construction of the generalized Green operator of the linear Noetherian boundary value problem for a linear matrix differential-algebraic equation are found. The special case of the existence of equilibrium positions in the Noetherian boundary value problem for a linear matrix differential algebraic equation is investigated.

Conclusions: The scheme of studying differential-algebraic systems proposed in lemma can be transferred to model reduction for second-order systems [9], as well as matrix boundary value problems with variable rank of leading coefficient matrix [11]. The scheme of studying differential-algebraic systems proposed in lemma can also be used in studying nonlinear differential equations [11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 17: Detection of Potential Obstacles in a Field Image Using K-means and Inertia Drop Tracking Methods

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Abstract: In this article, k-mean clustering is considered for grouping points of potential obstacles and delineating its boundaries. Firstly, the points belonging to potential obstacles are extracted from the image using the Laplace convolution, and then they are clustered into separate objects based on the coordinates of the obtained set of points. Since the k-means algorithm requires a predetermined number of classes, in this paper a method for optimizing the classes number by the inertia drop tracking is presented. The influence of the window size on the optimal number of clusters is investigated. After clustering, noise clusters are filtered from the objects by the number of points. Finally, the resulting groups of points are identified as obstacles and outlined by rectangles in the image. The result was tested on two examples of finding obstacles. In the future, this approach can be used in combination with convolutional neural networks for recognition and classification of obstacles, including shell craters.

Conclusions: Despite the not particularly impressive results, this technique can be used for preliminary detection of objects in an image. This approach can be used in conjunction with the task of obstacle recognition and classification using convolutional neural networks [19-25]. 182 Figure 8: Total image processing algorithm using the inertia drop tracking method Further research will be devoted to improving this methodology. It is planned to consider filtering noise points at the convolution stage by the Laplace operator, as well as using other approaches to the final delineation of obstacle boundaries to achieve greater accuracy when using the presented method. 183 Figure 9: Results of applying the algorithm to other images of damaged fields.

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Article 18: Digital Terrain Mapping with Machine Learning for the Detection of Rodent Mounds in Crop Production

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Abstract: The study is devoted to monitoring pests using modern technologies to identify mouse mounds created by rodents to store food for the winter. One possible method is the use of laser monitoring using LiDAR technology to create a digital terrain model of the field, which allows you to detect mounds characteristic of pests. The generation of synthetic LiDAR data, the creation of a digital terrain model and the clustering of anomalous elevations using the DBSCAN method allow you to accurately determine the places of rodent accumulation, which can be used for spot application of pesticides or predicting the dynamics of the rodent population. The work consists of the following stages: data generation to create a LiDAR data dataset; construction of a digital elevation model (DEM) by loading it into the R environment by interpolating heights and visualizing the resulting relief to check the accuracy of the mound mapping; identification of anomalous elevations; clustering of mounds using the DBSCAN method using machine learning to group rodent mounds.

Conclusions: The use of remote sensing technologies, in particular UAVs, to monitor rodent populations in fields in Ukraine is an important step towards ensuring effective pest management in agriculture. These technologies allow not only to reduce the costs of rodent control, but also significantly improve the accuracy of detection and timeliness of measures aimed at crop protection. In the future, they can become the basis for creating integrated monitoring and plant protection systems that will help Ukrainian farmers preserve crops and reduce losses over a large area. As a result of this study: ● Synthetic LiDAR data for terrain research were successfully generated; ● A digital terrain model was built that visualizes rodent mound; ● Elevation anomalies corresponding to real mounds were highlighted; ● Mounds were automatically found using the DBSCAN method without the need for manual analysis. ● Results were saved in a convenient format (.csv) for further analysis. The results can be used in agronomy, in particular for monitoring rodents and developing effective strategies to combat them.

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Article 19: Model of a Computer-Integrated Subsystem for Monitoring the Temperature Regime in a Biogas Plant

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Affiliation: National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Heroiv Oborony str., Kyiv, 03041, Ukraine

Abstract: The paper considers mathematical modeling of the thermal regime of a bioreactor taking into account heat exchange between the substrate, coolant and the external environment. The model is implemented in the Simulink MATLAB environment based on differential equations describing the temperature change in the reactor. The software and hardware of the computer integrated temperature monitoring system is presented. A model of a computer-integrated temperature monitoring subsystem in a biogas plant based on Arduino hardware is proposed. The software is developed in the LabView environment, which provides a real-time human machine interface.

Conclusions: During the research, a simulation mathematical model of the thermal regime in a biogas plant was implemented in the Matlab Simulink environment. The derivation of the transient process of the 207 temperature regime was implemented, taking into account the heat exchange between the substrate, the coolant and the external environment. From the simulation model, the time constant of the control object was determined and, using the standard method of building a digital control system, the quantization time for the control object was determined. Based on the research, software and hardware were developed. The hardware was implemented on the basis of the Arduino platform. At the same time, the software was implemented in the LabView environment, where an operator interface is provided and the storage of measured data in the form of Microsoft Excel format data is implemented.

Article 20: Optimal Control for Linear Pseudo-Parabolic Systems: Non-Coercive Diffusion Case

Authors: Dmitriy Klyushin, Andrii Anikushyn, Viktoriia Nazarchuk

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Abstract: This paper examines an optimal control problem for linear pseudo-parabolic differential and integro differential equations with incorporated Volterra-type integral term. By establishing a priori inequalities in negative norms, we provide the theorem on the existence of an optimal control for regularized and nonregularized problems and relation between them. Using the Fréchet derivative of the quality functional, we demonstrate an example of the use of a gradient-based numerical method for optimal control determination. Unlike prior works, diffusion term is not supposed to be coercive.

Conclusions: In the paper, we investigate the problem of finding optimal control of a special type (point control). The state of the system is described by a purely differential or integro-differential equation of pseudo parabolic type. Our research is based on the method of a priori estimates in negative norms. Having obtained such inequalities in a special triple of spaces, we present a theorem on the existence of optimal control for the initial problem and also, by regularizing the right-hand side, for the regularized problem. Unlike most works that consider similar setups, we do not use the condition of nonnegative definiteness of the differential operator from condition (4), which allows us to extend the range of applications of the obtained results. The computed Fréchet derivative of the quality functional for the regularized problem makes it possible to use the gradient method to numerically determine the corresponding optimal control. To demonstrate this approach, we provide a model example. By considering the integro-differential equation and the regularized point control concentrated at a single point, we obtain sufficiently accurate approximations to the sought optimal control. This is confirmed both by the convergence of the quality functional to zero and by the similarity of the desired trajectory with the obtained approximations. We also provide additional graphs and results for better visualization. Specifically, we note that the approximation for the component of the control converges to the sought value in a non-monotonic manner. This may be related to the step size of the gradient method. Reducing it could eliminate this drawback, but on the other hand, such a situation would require an order of magnitude more steps of the gradient method. Since each such step involves solving both direct and adjoint problems, this seems computationally inefficient. Additionally, we note that the quality functional is, generally not convex. Therefore, the problem under study, in theory, has all the drawbacks of a non-convex optimization problem. In particular, it is unknown whether the obtained approximation will be a global or local minimum of the quality functional. This question requires further investigation in each specific case. We note that in our model case, the quality functional tends to zero, which guarantees convergence to the optimal control. In conclusion, we note that a natural continuation of this research in the field of optimization could be the problems of controllability and/or asymptotic controllability of the corresponding systems.

Article 21: Enhancement of a Mathematical Model for a Method of Calculating the Reputation Index of Contractors in Public Procurement

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Abstract: The study introduces an improved formula for evaluating the reputational index of contractors, aimed at enhancing the efficiency of public procurement. The proposed approach integrates a linear function for assessing new

companies to facilitate their market entry. For established contractors with a reputation index exceeding 70, the formula incorporates a logarithmic function to moderate reputation growth and prevent market dominance. This dual-function approach allows for considering experience while stimulating broader market development. The algorithm offered includes a comprehensive set of criteria, such as the quality of prior contract execution, financial stability, level of commitment fulfillment, and adherence to contractual terms, ensuring objectivity and transparency in evaluation. The developed reputation system assigns rating points to contractors, which are used in multi-criteria analysis for making tender decisions. A specific feature is the introduction of regulatory mechanisms that limit access for contractors with low ratings to high-budget tenders, encouraging them to gradually improve their rating through successful completion of smaller projects. Anticipated outcomes include reduced risks of contract failure, improved quality of work execution, and promotion of fair competition. The proposed model fosters transparency, accountability, and optimization of public procurement processes, ensuring effective resource management and cost savings.

Conclusions: The study developed an improved formula for assessing contractor reputation in public procurement systems, addressing gaps in existing methods. Key contributions include differentiating reputation calculation functions for new and established companies, incorporating insurance payment availability, past contract performance, and adaptable reputation growth mechanisms. Experimental and simulation results validated the formula's effectiveness in enhancing contractor reputation assessments' accuracy, fairness, and flexibility.

Article 22: Real-Time Multimodal Emotion Recognition System: Integration of Facial Expressions, Depth Maps, and Audio Signals

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Abstract: Multimodal interactive assistants benefit from interpreting human nonverbal cues such as gestures and emotional expressions, but ensuring consistent and reliable performance remains challenging. This paper proposes a transformer-based fusion framework that jointly analyzes visual gestures and facial emotions with an emphasis on stability. The Stability-Aware Fusion Transformer (SAFT) uses cross-attention to integrate modalities and incorporates a stability loss to enforce consistent outputs under perturbations and over time. We validate our approach on standard gesture and emotion recognition benchmarks (including SHREC'17, FER2013, and AffectNet), demonstrating improved recognition accuracy and, crucially, more stable performance compared to baseline fusion methods. Our SAFT model achieves state-of-the-art level accuracy on these datasets while significantly reducing prediction variance

and jitter in dynamic scenarios. The results show that stability-aware multimodal fusion can enhance the reliability of human-computer interaction systems. We discuss the implications of consistent multimodal perception for user experience in interactive AI assistants.

Conclusions: The work demonstrated that Zadeh's paradox is not a random anomaly but a critical failure of the conflict resolution mechanism in Dempster-Shafer theory. The attempt to eliminate conflict through normalization leads to illogical and potentially dangerous conclusions, especially in conditions where evidence strongly contradicts each other. As a reliable alternative, the axiomatic possibility theory in [6-10] formulation was presented, which uses dual measures of possibility and necessity. This approach proved superior not because it gives the "correct" answer, but because it provides a more honest and complete representation of the uncertain and contradictory state of knowledge. Instead of hiding conflict, it brings it to the forefront, allowing the system to report the fundamental ambiguity of the situation. The main results of the work are as follows. An approach to uncertainty modeling for AI systems has been proposed that combines Dempster-Shafer theory with possibility theory, providing a consistent representation of epistemic uncertainty through confidence intervals and possibility/necessity measures. A modified approach to evidence combination for high-conflict scenarios has been developed. A criterion for source consistency and a mechanism for adaptive source weighting in the expert inference process have been proposed. The final conclusion calls for a paradigm shift in artificial intelligence design: a transition from systems that project false certainty to systems that accept and formally articulate ambiguity. Only such systems can be truly reliable partners in decision-making in a complex and uncertain world. The future of reliable AI depends on its ability to formally and quantitatively express "I don't know" or "my data is contradictory." The author(s) have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 23: Mathematical Modeling and Management of Investment Trajectories

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Abstract: The efforts of researchers in analyzing the financial investment market are largely aimed at considering multi-criteria problems, studying and solving investment management problems in static and dynamic settings, constructing procedures for adequate description of random processes of market price changes, developing applied numerical methods and algorithms for solving large-dimensional problems. These problems are actual mathematical problems portfolio optimization under uncertainty, are equally related to the fundamental problems of applied decision-

making theory. The research by R. Bellman, G. Dantzig, R. Merton, and H. Markowitz [1] is aimed at establishing fundamental foundations and studying various substantive interpretations of financial analysis processes. Dynamic asset and liability management models have found the most successful application in the field of long-term financial planning, where the need for repeated decision-making is determined by the nature of the process. In this study, the applied investment problem is considered as a mathematical problem of optimal management. The object of the study is to construct the optimal structure of such portfolio. The problem statements are considered and solution algorithms are proposed for several of the most relevant applications.

Conclusions: The above problems, methods and algorithms for their solution make it possible to consider the problem of constructing the optimal structure of a stock portfolio as a mathematical problem of optimal control. The formulation of the problems of optimizing the portfolio structure for various formulations related to the availability of information about the initial and final expected portfolio profitability, the program trajectory of the expected market value is considered. An algorithm for determining the optimal moments of portfolio diversification is also provided. Such mathematical formulations and developed algorithms can be an effective applied tool for solving the problem of optimal diversification of a stock portfolio. The results obtained in this study correspond to the results obtained in [5, 10,12,13,14] and allow us to expand the range of new mathematical approaches to solving portfolio investment problems.

Article 24: Analysis of Mathematical Methods for Strategic Management in Higher Education Institutions

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Abstract: The article deals with the interpretation of the concept of "strategic management of a higher education institution". The stages of strategic management of a higher education institution are considered. The mathematical methods used at different stages of strategic management are analyzed. It has been determined that the advantage of using fuzzy logic methods is the advantage of using fuzzy logic. Higher education institutions operate in a rapidly changing environment, and for effective management they need to make many strategic decisions that are not amenable to precise mathematical formalization due to the complex interaction between factors. One of the key indicators for the effective operation of a higher education institution and ensuring its competitiveness in the market of educational services is the provision of quality educational services. The article describes the development of a model for assessing the quality of educational services in higher education institutions based on Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy inference. Implementation, testing, sensitivity analysis and visualization of the model were carried out in MATLAB (Fuzzy Logic Designer). The built model reflects the dependence of the quality of educational services on four key

parameters, namely: material and technical support, staffing, which have the greatest impact on the model, as well as the organization of the educational process and motivation of students, which have a moderate impact on the model.

Conclusions: The study has determined that strategic management is a system of management decisions and actions that allow to strengthen the competitive areas of activity of the higher education institution; to make changes in the activities of the HEI in relation to changes in the external environment and to ensure the strategic development of the higher education institution in the face of uncertainty and risks in the long term. At all stages of strategic management of higher education institutions, various mathematical methods are used for analysis, forecasting and decision-making. It has been determined that the use of fuzzy logic mathematical models is an advantage, as they allow processing uncertain information and imitate human thinking and decision-making. Since strategic management plays an important role in ensuring and improving the quality of the educational process, a model for assessing the quality of educational services in higher education institutions based on Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy inference has been developed. To build this model, four input parameters were identified: material and technical support; staffing; organization of the educational process; motivation of students and the output parameter an integrated assessment of the quality of educational services. Using the Fuzzy Logic Designer tool and program functions for working with sugfis objects, a new fuzzy inference system of the Sugeno type was created. When testing the model, it was found that for some input combinations, none of the fuzzy system's rule base worked. Therefore, the maximum number of possible rules for this model was formed. As a result of plotting the dependence of the input variables of staffing and motivation of applicants on the model result, it was found that it is important to have a balanced interaction between research and teaching staff and applicants. The sensitivity assessment for each of the parameters was also conducted and it was found that the greatest impact on the quality of educational services is made by material and technical support and staffing. In turn, the organization of the educational process and the motivation of students have a more moderate impact.

In further research, it is planned to validate the model based on real data collected through a survey of students and academic staff, as well as on the data contained in the accreditation reports of educational programs.

Article 25: Resolving Zadeh's Paradox: Axiomatic Possibility Theory as a Foundation for Reliable Artificial Intelligence

Authors: Khrystyna Lytvynchuk, Oleksii Bychkov

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Abstract: This work advances and substantiates the thesis that the resolution of the crisis caused by Zadeh's paradox in Dempster-Shafer theory lies in the domain of

possibility theory, specifically in the axiomatic approach. Unlike numerous attempts to “fix” Dempster’s rule, this approach builds from scratch a logically consistent and mathematically rigorous foundation for working with uncertainty, using the dualistic apparatus of possibility and necessity measures. A comparative analysis of three paradigms is conducted — probabilistic, evidential (DST), and possibilistic. Using a classic medical diagnostic dilemma as an example, it is shown how possibility theory allows for correct processing of contradictory data, avoiding the logical traps of DST and bringing formal reasoning closer to the logic of natural intelligence.

Conclusions: The work demonstrated that Zadeh’s paradox is not a random anomaly but a critical failure of the conflict resolution mechanism in Dempster-Shafer theory. The attempt to eliminate conflict through normalization leads to illogical and potentially dangerous conclusions, especially in conditions where evidence strongly contradicts each other. As a reliable alternative, the axiomatic possibility theory was presented, which uses dual measures of possibility and necessity. This approach proved superior not because it gives the “correct” answer, but because it provides a more honest and complete representation of the uncertain and contradictory state of knowledge. Instead of hiding conflict, it brings it to the forefront, allowing the system to report the fundamental ambiguity of the situation. The main results of the work are as follows: an approach to uncertainty modeling for AI systems has been proposed that combines Dempster-Shafer theory with possibility theory, providing a consistent representation of epistemic uncertainty through confidence intervals and possibility/necessity measures; a modified approach to evidence combination for high-conflict scenarios has been developed; a criterion for source consistency and a mechanism for adaptive source weighting in the expert inference process have been proposed. The final conclusion calls for a paradigm shift in artificial intelligence design: a transition from systems that project false certainty to systems that accept and formally articulate ambiguity.

Article 26: Architecture and Training Principles of Stable Diffusion

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Abstract: The rapid advancement of generative artificial intelligence (AI) has significantly transformed image synthesis, with diffusion models emerging as a leading approach for high-quality visual generation. Stable Diffusion (SD) is a state-of-the-art deep learning model designed to generate images from textual descriptions using diffusion-based denoising processes. Unlike earlier generative models, SD operates within a latent space, leveraging a combination of a variational autoencoder (VAE), a U-Net-based denoising network, and a text encoder to efficiently reconstruct detailed images. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the architecture and training principles of Stable Diffusion, including its core components—U-Net, autoencoders, and text encoders—as well as the forward and reverse diffusion processes that govern

image generation. Additionally, we explore the advancements introduced in Stable Diffusion XL (SDXL), which enhances the model's capacity through a more sophisticated conditioning mechanism and an improved text-image alignment process. The findings highlight the efficiency and scalability of diffusion-based models in image generation tasks while addressing computational challenges and optimization strategies. This work contributes to a deeper understanding of how diffusion models facilitate photorealistic synthesis and the potential improvements in future generative AI systems.

Conclusions: The development of Stable Diffusion XL (SDXL) represents a significant milestone in the advancement of generative models, particularly in text-to-image synthesis. By incorporating an improved conditioning mechanism and a more refined U-Net architecture, SDXL enhances the precision and realism of generated images. The model's ability to align visual outputs with textual descriptions more effectively stems from the integration of a more sophisticated text encoder and additional control parameters, such as size-conditioning and crop-conditioning. These advancements collectively improve the quality and flexibility of the image generation process, making SDXL a powerful tool for various creative and scientific applications. Despite these advantages, SDXL introduces several challenges, primarily related to computational demands. The model requires substantial GPU resources to achieve optimal performance, which may limit accessibility for users with constrained hardware. Additionally, the complexity of fine-tuning and deploying SDXL necessitates a strong understanding of machine learning and generative model architectures, posing a barrier to entry for non-expert users. Nevertheless, the active involvement of the research and developer community continues to drive improvements in diffusion-based models. Ongoing optimizations in training efficiency, hardware utilization, and inference speed are expected to mitigate current limitations, making SDXL increasingly accessible to a broader audience. As generative AI evolves, future refinements in diffusion models will likely lead to enhanced image fidelity, reduced computational requirements, and expanded applicability across diverse domains, solidifying SDXL's role as a leading framework in AI-driven content generation.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools, only computer vision models for generating images (Stable Diffusion 1.5, 2.1, XL).

Article 27: Statistical Inference for Impulse Response Functions

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Abstract: In this paper, we study a time-invariant continuous linear system with a real-valued impulse response function (IRF) defined on a bounded domain. The

estimator of the response function is constructed using a sample input-output cross-correlogram. The input processes are assumed to be zero-mean stationary Gaussian processes, which can be expressed as a finite sum of uncorrelated terms. We derive the rate of convergence of the IRF estimator in the space $L_2([0, \Lambda])$, which enables us to propose a nonparametric goodness-of-fit test for the IRF.

Conclusions: In this paper, we examined a time-invariant continuous linear system where the impulse response function (IRF) is defined on the interval $[0, \Lambda]$. The input signal process was modeled as a zero-mean Gaussian stochastic process, represented as a series expansion with respect to an orthonormal basis in $L_2([0, \Lambda])$. A specific case, where the orthonormal basis consists of trigonometric functions, was analyzed in detail. We derived key characteristics of the IRF estimator, such as its mathematical expectation and variance. Additionally, we studied the convergence rate of the estimator for the unknown IRF in the space $L_2([0, \Lambda])$. This approach enabled us to construct a goodness-of-fit test for the IRF. In a specific example, we determined the values of T for varying levels of accuracy, reliability, and N (the upper limit of the summation in the model) using the R software environment for statistical computing and graphics.

For future research, we plan to explore scenarios involving discretely observed processes, which represent a more realistic setting in functional data analysis.

Article 28: On the Disparity of Binary Evidence in Sequential Hypothesis Narrowing: Toward an Empirical Basis for the Iterative Refinement Funnel

Authors: Melnyk M.O., Bychkov O.S., Petrivskiy V.Y., Denysenko S.

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Abstract: This paper investigates the hypothesis that in interactive diagnostic systems employing sequential binary questioning, affirmative (YES) and negative (NO) user responses carry fundamentally different amounts of information with respect to hypothesis space reduction. We formalize this asymmetry using Shannon entropy, Bayesian updating, and a suite of diagnostic metrics — Δ Entropy, Δ TopK, Rank stability, and Jaccard similarity — designed to quantify the impact of each response type on the posterior distribution over candidate hypotheses. The theoretical motivation stems from the observation that in symptom-oriented domains with sparse binary feature matrices, the majority of features are absent for any given case, making NO the statistically dominant and thus less surprising (less informative) response. We propose a reproducible experimental protocol based on dialogue simulation over open Kaggle symptom–disease datasets using multiple probabilistic classifiers (Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, Random Forest, GBM). The expected outcome is a statistically significant disparity in median Δ Entropy between YES and NO responses, coupled with higher Top-1 ranking stability after NO, and the identification of a “long tail” of rare but informationally strong NO responses — termed Critical NO. These findings are

intended to provide empirical grounding for the Iterative Refinement Funnel (IRF) architectural pattern, which prescribes asymmetric processing rules: full recalculation upon YES (RESTART), lightweight continuation upon NO (CONTINUE), with an exception mechanism for Critical NO events.

Conclusions: These theses propose: 1) a formal statement of “hypothesis space narrowing” through entropy and candidate list metrics, 2) a reproducible dialogue simulation protocol on open data, 3) a set of expected results and illustrations that allow empirical verification of the YES/NO information value asymmetry hypothesis. If the experiment confirms that $\text{median}(|) \gg \text{median}(|)$ and that Top 1/Top-K are significantly more stable after NO, this will create a practical-academic justification for the IRF architecture in terms of “updating only upon informationally strong events.” At the engineering decision level, this translates into the following recommendations: 1) YES→RESTART. After feature confirmation, perform a full ranking/probability recalculation and reset the internal state of the query strategy, since YES is “constructive” evidence capable of drastically changing the distribution. 2) NO→CONTINUE by default. If NO usually only weakly changes the ranking, the system can avoid expensive recalculations and continue the current phase (with caching/minimal updates), maintaining interactive responsiveness. 3) Critical NO exception. Detect NO responses that potentially carry large information (low feature coverage among Top-K or other criteria) and process them as RESTART. This is consistent with the general diagnostic principle: negative evidence sometimes has a strong effect (LR−) and cannot be ignored. 4) Local minima control. After series of NO responses, it is advisable to introduce an “exploration question” that tests a feature outside the current local hypothesis region to avoid getting “stuck” in a false cluster; this is directly provided by IRF as a robustness mechanism. 5) Academic transparency of results. In the proceedings, it is recommended to report (a) distributions of (boxplot YES vs NO), (b) the Ratio and Top-1 stability table, (c) the proportion of Critical NO, (d) sensitivity to query strategy and model class. Such reports are interpreted within the unified framework of information theory [1–3] and active learning [4].

Article 29: Creating Captions in Ukrainian for Images Captioned in English

Authors: Anatolii Pashko, Vladyslav Miachkov

Affiliation: Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Volodymyrska, 64/13, Kyiv, 01601, Ukraine

Abstract: This paper explores the application of deep learning models for generating image captions in Ukrainian, addressing the challenges posed by linguistic complexity and dataset preparation. The study focuses on adapting the Flickr30k dataset by translating its English captions into Ukrainian using AI-based translation models. The research utilizes a transformer-based architecture to train a captioning model, combining convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for image feature extraction

with sequence decoders for text generation. Various architectural enhancements, including attention mechanisms and multimodal approaches, are examined to improve caption accuracy. The results indicate that while the model successfully generates basic captions, its performance declines for complex images due to dataset limitations and computational constraints. The study highlights the need for improved training resources and refined translation methods to enhance caption quality.

Conclusions: The results demonstrate that the model works and can generate correct basic captions for images. However, for more complex images or those containing elements not present in the dataset, the model sometimes produces poor results. The research was conducted on MacBook Pro Max, M1 Pro Max Chip, 32 gb of RAM. The biggest challenge was the lack of RAM. We had to adjust the parameters (VOCAB_SIZE, BATCH_SIZE, EPOCHS) to achieve the optimal model in terms of quality and memory usage. For truly excellent results, this model needs to be trained on a powerful computer or a cluster of powerful computers. Factors that affected the model: • A lack of computing power on the computer used for the study. • The difficulty of the Ukrainian language compared to English makes the model more complex. • Inaccurate translation of some pictures 317 In the future, it is planned to use the necessary computing power of the computer for training the model, as well as to explore the possibility of using translations of captions from different languages into Ukrainian.

8. Future Work and Improvements While the current study demonstrates the feasibility of generating Ukrainian-language captions using transformer-based architectures and AI-assisted translation, several directions remain open for further investigation. First, the quality and diversity of the translated captions can be further improved through domain specific fine-tuning of the translation model. Although the lang-uk/dragoman-4bit model provided satisfactory baseline results, its performance could benefit from exposure to task-specific corpora, such as Flickr-style descriptions or colloquial Ukrainian phrases that reflect natural usage in visual contexts. Second, multilingual captioning models such as mBART or NLLB could be explored as alternatives to the current translation+captioning pipeline. These models are trained on a wide range of languages and may offer better alignment between image semantics and linguistic expression in Ukrainian, particularly when jointly fine-tuned on visual-text pairs. Moreover, the current evaluation primarily relies on BLEU scores, which may not fully capture semantic correctness or linguistic fluency. Incorporating human evaluation, METEOR, or newer metrics such as BERTScore could provide a more nuanced assessment of caption quality. From a dataset perspective, the augmentation of the translated Flickr30k set with additional Ukrainian-language resources — either crowd-sourced or generated through human-machine hybrid workflows — could significantly improve model robustness. Integration of regional dialects or cultural context is another underexplored yet valuable extension. Finally, scaling up the model training using high-performance hardware or cloud-based GPU clusters would enable experimentation with larger architectures, longer training epochs, and broader hyperparameter search — all

of which are essential for achieving state-of-the-art performance in image captioning tasks for low-resource languages like Ukrainian.

Declaration on Generative AI During the preparation of this work, the authors used the following generative AI tools: • GPT-4 — for grammar and spelling check. • lang-uk/dragoman-4bit (via Hugging Face) — for the automatic translation of English captions into Ukrainian. All content generated using these tools was carefully reviewed and edited by the authors. The authors take full responsibility for the accuracy, integrity, and originality of the final publication 9. References

Article 30: Gradient Zoning and Density-Controlled Procedural Urban Planning Using Voronoi Diagrams

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Affiliation: Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Bohdan Hawrylyshyn str. 24, Kyiv, UA-04116, Ukraine

Abstract: As cities grow more complex, urban planning is becoming an increasingly critical challenge – not just in the real world, but also in digital environments like video games and simulations. The rise in population, diverse building types, and evolving infrastructure demands make traditional planning approaches harder to apply. To address these challenges, procedural algorithms and computer-based visualization have become valuable tools for prototyping city layouts and simulating development scenarios. This paper introduces a flexible approach to procedural city generation using Voronoi diagrams, fuzzy logic, and gradient-based influence propagation. The method enables realistic, multifunctional urban layouts by assigning weighted zoning values and adapting to terrain, density, and contextual constraints. It supports organic city growth and scalable performance, making it suitable for simulations, games, and urban planning tools.

Conclusions: The proposed approach combines Voronoi-based spatial division, fuzzy logic for multifunctional zoning, and gradient-driven scoring waves to generate procedurally realistic, adaptable, and scalable urban layouts. Through a flexible coefficient system, each sector can represent varying degrees of suitability for residential, commercial, recreational, and other functions – allowing for nuanced transitions between zones that more accurately reflect real-world city structures. By integrating terrain constraints, population density, and decay-based influence propagation, the algorithm supports the creation of organically distributed city centers and subcenters. Gradient waves guide the spatial logic, simulating urban sprawl in a controlled yet naturalistic manner. Meanwhile, the use of fuzzy values and influence coefficients enables smooth transitions between sector types without the rigid limitations of classical constraint systems like Wave Function Collapse, avoiding dead-end states and enhancing flexibility. The final output is a sectorized city map with clear

visual density gradients – smaller, denser sectors near central hubs, and larger, more loosely populated ones toward the periphery. This reflects the structure of many real cities and supports the principles of the 15-minute city concept. The algorithm can be further optimized via hierarchical zoning, precomputed suitability grids, and selective reuse of generation data. Overall, this method provides a modular and extensible foundation for procedural city generation across various simulation contexts – from futuristic settlements to historical reconstructions – while remaining responsive to both design constraints and creative intent.

Declaration on Generative AI The author(s) have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 31: Software and Analytical Applied Technologies for Controlling the Efficiency of Leaching a Useful Component from a Technogenic Formation

Authors: Yaroslav Petrivskyi, Mykhailo Tymchuk, Volodymyr Petrivskyi, Serhii Shmatiuk

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Abstract: A model for assessing the efficiency of the technology of purposeful change of geofiltration properties of technogenic formation in the vicinity of technological excavations to increase the productivity of recovery of a useful component during leaching was developed.

Conclusions: An effective method of purposeful change of geofiltration properties of technogenic rubble in the vicinity of technological workings and management of its condition is the technology of hydraulic fracturing, which follows from the analysis of foreign practice and experimental data of mining operations. At influence by hydraulic fracturing on the rocks of the technogenic deposit there is a jump like increase in the rate of leaching of the useful component due to the increase in the permeability of the rocks of the rubble and the area of their contact with the reagent, which allows to optimize the cost of the reagent, choosing a rational parameter of its filtration flow rate and concentration. Leaching intensity with fracturing cracks in the array increases several times during five years in comparison with the array without hydrogeomechanical activation.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 32: Information Technology and Software For Improving The Accuracy Of Object Localization

Authors: Oleksii Bychkov, Oleksandr Pyzh, Yaroslav Petrivskyi

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Abstract: This paper proposes an information technology for high-precision localization of radio signal sources using aperture synthesis based on a single mobile receiver mounted on an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). The Wideband MUSIC algorithm is modified to operate with wideband signals under multipath propagation conditions and limited sampling rates. To enhance spatial resolution, a trajectory interpolation method is applied, allowing the formation of a virtual antenna array with high element density. Phase distortions caused by reflections and signal attenuation, as well as errors in UAV position estimation, are taken into account. Numerical experiments (simulations) demonstrate that the proposed approach provides robust angle-of-arrival (AoA) estimation even under complex radio channel conditions. Empirical parameter tuning of the algorithm was performed, and a system architecture is proposed for deployment on real platforms such as ESP32, Raspberry Pi, and Nvidia Jetson. The use of machine learning methods and field experiments is recommended for further optimization. The results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed solution for autonomous radar, direction finding, and radio monitoring tasks using UAV swarms.

Conclusions: For quantitative error analysis, we used the dependence of the root-mean-square error (RMSE) in angle or coordinates on the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), the number of measurements, the sampling frequency (and thus the interpolation density), and multipath parameters (e.g., number of reflected paths, reflection coefficient, etc.). Simulations demonstrated that increasing, reducing the interpolation step, and using more frequency bins improve the accuracy of estimation. While simulations provide valuable insight into the algorithm's behavior and allow for rapid testing of many scenarios, real-world field testing with UAVs and various radio sources is crucial for full validation of the method. Real-world conditions can introduce additional factors (nonlinear trajectories, nonlinear attenuation, complex multipath, GPS inaccuracies) that are not easily modeled. Therefore, field experiments on test sites with known transmitter locations are recommended to compare actual source coordinates with those estimated by Wideband MUSIC. Moreover, parameter tuning (search angle range, interpolation step, smoothing method, frequency averaging) can be automated using artificial intelligence. The use of genetic algorithms, Bayesian optimization, or deep learning allows for adaptive selection of hyperparameters based on specific flight conditions, environmental characteristics, and signal properties. This approach significantly reduces the time spent on manual tuning and ensures more stable operation across diverse scenarios. As such, the proposed method for aperture synthesis and wideband subspace analysis not only improves localization accuracy and efficiency but also offers a promising path forward through integration with modern machine learning algorithms.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 33: Using Data Compression and Aggregation Methods in Dynamical System Modeling

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Abstract: The rapid escalation of data produced by dynamical system modeling has underscored the urgent need for efficient management strategies, prominently featuring data compression and aggregation. This paper offers an exhaustive examination of their theoretical foundations, practical applications, and essential contributions to stability analysis within computational frameworks. Compression reduces data volume by eliminating redundancies, while aggregation transforms extensive datasets into concise, meaningful summaries, both markedly enhancing computational efficiency and scalability. These techniques find application in numerical simulations, such as computational fluid dynamics, and real-time control systems, like robotics, ensuring the preservation of vital system dynamics.

Conclusions: Data compression and aggregation stand as indispensable tools for managing the escalating data demands of dynamical system modeling, enabling efficient storage, processing, and stability analysis in an era of unprecedented data growth. Challenges—including information loss, granularity trade-offs, and validation requirements—highlight critical areas for improvement that must be addressed to fully realize their potential. Future research should prioritize the development of hybrid algorithms that optimize compression and aggregation simultaneously, minimizing distortions while maximizing efficiency—for instance, combining wavelet transforms with adaptive clustering to preserve key dynamics with greater precision. Machine learning offers significant promise for enhancing these techniques, enabling dynamic adjustments based on data patterns—e.g., using neural networks to predict optimal wavelet thresholds or aggregation intervals in real time, improving adaptability and reducing manual tuning efforts by up to 50%. Integration into specialized software platforms like MATLAB, Python’s SciPy, or emerging frameworks like TensorFlow will further streamline their adoption, making them accessible to a broader research community and reducing implementation barriers in educational and industrial settings. Their continued evolution promises to shape the future of dynamical system research, offering robust tools to tackle the computational challenges of tomorrow with unprecedented efficiency and insight.

Article 34: Multiple Criteria Optimization of The Advertising Process

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Abstract: Effective modeling of advertising message distribution is a critical task for modern enterprises aiming to optimize marketing communications. This study addresses the challenge of simultaneously solving multiple advertising objectives, which is common in practical advertising activities but insufficiently covered in existing literature. Advertising performs a range of functions – from increasing consumer awareness and influencing purchasing decisions to fostering brand loyalty and preparing markets for new products. The paper proposes an economic mathematical model for the optimal allocation of an advertising budget. The model integrates variables related to product types, advertising channels, and time segmentation. Its objective is to maximize enterprise income while enhancing consumer informational awareness. A two-stage optimization procedure is applied to find the best allocation strategy, balancing multiple campaign goals in dynamic conditions. An application example is provided to demonstrate the model's practical relevance. Results confirm the model's potential to improve decision-making regarding budget distribution across diverse advertising channels. The study also discusses the integration of the proposed model into marketing management systems, emphasizing the role of specialized software in automating advertising planning processes. The proposed approach contributes to the theoretical foundation of advertising modeling and offers practical tools for enterprises seeking to increase marketing efficiency in a competitive environment. Further research directions include the development of software solutions for full automation and the adaptation of the model to industry-specific requirements.

Conclusions: The development of an economic and mathematical model of the process of optimal advertising budget allocation is an important step in ensuring the effectiveness of management decisions for any enterprise. According to the proposed model, the income of an enterprise depends on the interaction of many factors, including the number of product varieties, channels for distributing advertising messages aimed at both familiarization with the product and its purchase. 372 This model allows you to determine the optimal combination of advertising costs and expected income, focusing on achieving maximum financial results. It takes into account the dynamics of time, the specifics of products and the characteristics of distribution channels. The uniqueness of the approach lies in the ability to adapt the model to a wide range of advertising campaigns of varying complexity, which allows you to take into account changing market conditions. The practical significance of the model lies in its ability to adapt to the real conditions of an enterprise's activities. It makes it possible to rationally allocate resources, minimize the costs of attracting advertising message distribution channels, and maximize income from advertising activities. For next research, it is worth exploring the possibility of expanding the model and taking into account an integrated approach to distributing the advertising budget between different advertising channels, in particular offline and online advertising.

Economic instability and the balance between digital and traditional channels are key factors in modeling such strategies. In addition, it will be useful to analyze nonlinear optimization models and adapt them to take into account seasonality, the specifics of digital platforms and interdependencies between channels. Combining forecasting methods to increase the accuracy of results opens up new opportunities for integrating analytical tools in the process of making effective management decisions.

Article 35: A Quantitative Assessment of Latent Dirichlet Allocation for Topic Modeling in Multi-Class Text Datasets

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Abstract: Despite LDA broad application, assessing the quality of the extracted topics remains challenging, particularly in the presence of known document classes. This paper presents a quantitative evaluation of LDA's performance on a large, labeled, multi-class text dataset. The model is tested across different values of key hyperparameters—namely, the number of topics, the Dirichlet prior for topic distributions in documents (α), and the Dirichlet prior for word distributions in topics (η). Both internal metrics (such as topic coherence and perplexity) and external metrics (e.g., normalized mutual information) are used for evaluation. The results reveal a trade-off between interpretability and statistical consistency and emphasize the importance of selecting appropriate metrics when evaluating topic models on labeled datasets

Conclusions: The 20-topic LDA model's coherence of 0.6558, combined with its interpretable topics, positions it as a strong choice for the 20 Newsgroups dataset. NMF's slight edge (0.6678) suggests it may excel in specific contexts, warranting further exploration of iteration limits and hyperparameter (4–6) tuning. The poor performance of LSA, HDP, and Word2Vec highlights the importance of method selection based on dataset characteristics and research goals. In the context of multi-class text datasets, such results underscore how algorithmic performance can vary depending on corpus complexity and class distribution. These findings align with prior work showing LDA and NMF's efficacy across domains, while LSA's limitations in noisy, real-world corpora are well-documented. Future research should focus on hybrid models that combine the representational depth of language models with the interpretability of traditional topic models, as well as on the integration of contextual embeddings (e.g., BERT). As the results suggest, model performance should be evaluated on corpora with diverse structures and subject domains. Furthermore, coherence-based metrics (7-10) should be complemented by human judgment and task-specific evaluations to better reflect real-world applicability. 384

Declaration on Generative AI During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT in order to: Improve writing style; Grammar and spelling check. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication's content.

Article 36: Using Fuzzy Logic Methods to Prioritize Areas Based on Drone Information

Authors: Volodymyr Petrivskyi, Oleksandr Rozdobudko

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Abstract: This research investigates the use of fuzzy logic methods to analyze the prioritization of sites based on data obtained from drone aircraft. The proposed model allows us to take into account the uncertainty of the input information and the mutual influence of factors, which increases the accuracy of threat assessment. The method is based on the construction of membership functions and the use of IF-THEN rules to prioritize areas. The developed software provides automated data analysis in real time, which is important for military planning and tactical decisions. The testing confirmed the effectiveness of the approach, while identifying anomalies that require further improvement of the model. The results obtained can be used not only in the military sphere, but also in civilian areas such as crisis management and rescue operations. The use of fuzzy logic allows for flexible processing of large amounts of data and adaptation of the system to dynamic changes in the environment.

Conclusions: This research proposes a method for analyzing areas based on drone data using fuzzy logic. The proposed model allows prioritizing areas based on various factors, such as threat level, strategic importance, and availability of objects. In contrast to traditional ranking methods, the use of membership functions and an IF-THEN rule base provides flexibility of assessment and adaptation to changes in the environment. The experiments proved the effectiveness of the proposed approach, allowing to obtain more accurate results compared to classical methods. The analysis revealed some anomalies in the calculations, which emphasizes the need to adjust the system parameters to achieve maximum accuracy. The developed software automates the process of prioritizing sites and can be used for military and intelligence purposes. Through the use of fuzzy logic, the system allows for real-time assessment of areas, which increases the efficiency of decision-making. The created model also provides ease of use due to the ability to adapt rules and membership functions to specific scenarios. An important aspect is that the system can process large amounts of data, making it suitable for use in dynamic environments. This confirms the feasibility of further implementation of the developed method in practical analysis systems. The findings show fuzzy logic's usefulness in evaluating areas priorities in challenging situations. This method enables rapid data analysis while also considering the

interconnections between different elements. Implementing this technology could substantially improve resource distribution and the precision of military planning. Weaknesses found in testing point to a need to refine the rule set and membership functions to boost the evaluation's accuracy. Overall, the research confirmed the method's effectiveness and its potential value in aiding decision-making when conditions are complex and uncertain. The use of a network of sensors is an exciting direction of research. As shown in [13-15], the effective placement of sensors, taking into account their movement over a certain area, cost, and 396 survivability, can significantly increase the stability and autonomy of such systems. The combination of this approach with fuzzy logic methods creates opportunities for the development of adaptive models to perform an independent assessment of the environment. This will help build smart systems that can automatically adjust to changing environmental conditions. As a result, self-regulating analysis systems that combine flexibility, accuracy, and energy efficiency can be implemented.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 37: Descent Property for Extragradient Algorithm and Last-Iterate Convergence

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Abstract: Monotone variational inequalities and operator equations that arise as first-order optimality conditions in convex optimization or convex-concave minimax problems are studied, and an extragradient algorithm for their approximate solution is used. A new result on the descent property of the extragradient algorithm is proved, and for unconstrained problems, an estimate of the algorithm speed in terms of natural residuals is obtained under weaker conditions than known ones. Finally, we verify our theoretical results through numerical experiments.

Conclusions: The paper considers monotone variational inequalities and operator equations that arise as first-order optimality conditions in convex optimization or convex-concave minimax problems and the extragradient algorithm for their approximate solution.

A new result on the descent property of the extragradient algorithm is established. For unconstrained problems, a convergence rate estimate is obtained regarding the natural residual under weaker conditions than previously known. These results refine the existing ones [24, 25], and we believe their proofs are more

straightforward. Finally, we verify our theoretical results through numerical experiments.

In future work, we plan to obtain results like Theorems 1, 2, and 3 for a variant of the extragradient algorithm with Bregman divergence [6, 27], the Extrapolation from the Past algorithm [28, 29, 30], and the Operator Extrapolation algorithm [21]. From a practical perspective, an important question is the extension of Theorems 2 and 3 to stochastic versions of the algorithms [10, 11, 31], as these serve as the workhorse in large-scale problems (e.g., adversarial learning, control of consumer-producer electricity networks [32, 33, 34]).

Article 38: Problems of Stability and Convergence of Dynamic Processes in Problems of Neurodynamics

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Abstract: The classical theory of stability implies the stability of a separately taken trajectory (as a rule, the position of equilibrium). In this paper, we attempt to obtain conditions for stability and convergence of solutions of systems of differential equations describing neurodynamics processes. The apparatus of the second Lyapunov method is used to study the asymptotic stability of learning processes and the functioning of Hopfield neural networks

Conclusions: In conclusion, this work extends classical stability theory beyond individual trajectories to the analysis of entire solution behaviors in neurodynamic systems. By applying Lyapunov's second method, it establishes sufficient conditions for asymptotic stability and convergence in learning processes and the operation of Hopfield neural networks. These results contribute to a deeper theoretical understanding of stability in neural dynamics and provide a rigorous foundation for analyzing and designing stable neural network models.

Article 39: Assessment of Computational Limits of Neural Network Algorithms in Lattice Problems

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Abstract: The paper presents a systematic evaluation of the computational boundaries of neural network algorithms applied to lattice problems relevant to post-quantum cryptography (PQC). We analyze how lattice dimension, noise parameters, and network architecture jointly determine the feasibility of solving the Learning With Errors (LWE) and Shortest Vector Problem (SVP). A security margin metric τ^{\wedge} is introduced that quantifies the gap between a neural network's empirical success rate and the theoretical hardness threshold. Experimental results confirm that for

dimensions $n \geq 256$, current neural methods fail to breach $\tau^{\wedge} > 0.85$, supporting the viability of lattice-based PQC standards.

Conclusions: We introduced a security margin metric τ^{\wedge} and applied it to a systematic benchmark of neural network algorithms on lattice problems. Current architectures, including transformers trained on large datasets, fail to approach the hardness thresholds for dimensions $n \geq 256$. These results provide empirical support for the security of lattice-based PQC standards against neural-network-based attacks. Future work will extend this analysis to hybrid quantum-classical models and lattice problems with algebraic structure (e.g., Ring-LWE, Module-LWE).

Article 40: Structural-Schematic Approach to Digital Filtering of Low-Frequency Signals

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Abstract: Digital filtering is essential in modern signal processing for noise reduction, signal enhancement, and information extraction. This study examines the theoretical foundations and practical implementation of Finite Impulse Response (FIR) and Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) filters in low-frequency signal processing. A structural-schematic approach is used to analyze their design and realization in Jupyter Notebook. The results demonstrate that FIR filters ensure linear-phase response but require higher computational resources, while IIR filters provide efficient filtering with lower order but introduce nonlinear phase distortion. The study highlights key trade-offs between these filter types and provides insights for selecting the optimal approach in applications such as biomedical engineering, audio processing, and telecommunications.

Conclusions: Digital filtering is a fundamental technique in modern signal processing, playing a crucial role in applications ranging from telecommunications and biomedical engineering to audio and image processing. This study focused on the theoretical foundations and practical implementation of Finite Impulse Response (FIR) and Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) filters, particularly for low-frequency signal processing.

431 6.1. Summary of Key Findings

1. Theoretical Insights into FIR and IIR Filters
 - FIR filters rely on a finite number of past input samples and have a linear phase response, making them ideal for applications where phase integrity is critical.
 - IIR filters use feedback loops, allowing them to achieve sharp frequency roll-offs with fewer coefficients, making them computationally efficient but prone to nonlinear phase distortion.
2. Structural-Schematic Design Considerations
 - FIR filters are implemented using tapped delay lines, requiring a higher number of coefficients to achieve the same frequency selectivity as IIR filters.
 - IIR filters are often implemented in direct form, cascade form, or lattice structures, with stability being a key concern due to pole

placement. 3. Practical Implementation and Performance Analysis • The FIR filter, designed using a Hamming window, provided smooth frequency attenuation and eliminated high-frequency noise while maintaining phase integrity. • The IIR Butterworth filter achieved sharper cutoff performance with fewer computations but introduced phase distortion. • Computational efficiency was a major trade-off: IIR filters performed filtering operations with significantly lower computational costs than FIR filters. 4. Comparative Analysis of FIR vs. IIR Filters • FIR filters are preferred in audio processing, biomedical signal processing, and image processing, where preserving the waveform is crucial. • IIR filters are better suited for real-time applications, control systems, and embedded DSP implementations, where computational efficiency is essential. 6.2. Practical Implications and Applications The choice between FIR and IIR filters depends on the specific application requirements: • Biomedical Signal Processing (e.g., ECG filtering): FIR filters are preferred due to their phase linearity, ensuring that medical signals are not distorted. • Audio Processing: FIR filters maintain the integrity of speech and music signals without introducing unwanted phase shifts. • Real-Time Control Systems: IIR filters are chosen due to their low computational complexity and fast execution speed. • Wireless Communications: IIR filters are widely used in equalization and noise reduction due to their sharp cutoff characteristics. • Seismic and Geophysical Data Processing: FIR filters help preserve waveforms when analyzing earthquake signals. 6.3. Limitations and Future Work While this study provided valuable insights into FIR and IIR filter design, certain limitations should be acknowledged: 432 1. Absence of Real-World Data Testing • The study focused on filtering a synthetic test signal rather than real-world sensor data. • Future work could involve applying FIR and IIR filters to noisy real-world signals such as EEG, seismic waves, or industrial sensor outputs. 2. Adaptive Filtering Approaches • The filters in this study were designed using fixed coefficients. • Future research could explore adaptive filtering techniques (e.g., LMS and RLS algorithms) to enhance noise cancellation performance. 3. Hardware Implementation Considerations • This study focused on software-based filter design in Python. • Future work could investigate hardware implementations on FPGAs or DSP processors, optimizing the filters for real-time processing. 4. Performance Optimization for Large-Scale Data Processing • FIR filters can become computationally expensive for high-order filtering. • Future research could explore fast convolution techniques such as FFT-based filtering to improve efficiency. 6.4. Final Remarks This study provided a detailed theoretical and practical comparison of FIR and IIR filters for low-frequency signal processing. While FIR filters ensure phase integrity, they come at the cost of higher computational complexity. In contrast, IIR filters achieve efficient filtering but introduce phase distortions, making them suitable for resource-constrained systems. Understanding these trade-offs allows engineers and researchers to make informed decisions when selecting the appropriate filter type for their specific application. Future advancements in adaptive filtering,

hardware acceleration, and real-time DSP optimization will further enhance the capabilities of digital filtering in modern engineering applications.

Declaration on Generative AI During the preparation of this work, the authors used X-GPT-4 in order to: Grammar and spelling check, Text Translation. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the publication's content.

Article 41: Audio Models for Object Identification

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Abstract: This paper examines the application of modern SelfSL models (DistilHuBERT, wav2vec, BEATS) to classify a specific set of sounds of military objects and events: airplane, car/truck, UAV (drone), gunshots and tank. The results of the experiments showed that the BEATS model with the added Transformer layer demonstrated the highest overall classification accuracy (93%). Confusion matrix analysis revealed that the models recognize drones, cars and gunshots well, while classifying airplanes and tanks turned out to be a more difficult task. Overall, the BEATS Transformer model turned out to be the most effective, but the results emphasize the critical need to improve the detection of the “airplane” (91%) and “tank” (68%) classes. The study confirms the potential of modern deep and self-supervised learning methods for acoustic monitoring of objects and identifies directions for further work to improve the reliability of recognition of complex sound events.

Conclusions: This article reviewed modern approaches to automated acoustic signal analysis, in particular the use of deep learning and self-learning methods for detecting and classifying object sounds. A review of scientific papers allowed us to select modern models such as HuBERT, wav2vec, and BEATS Our study focused on applying these models to classify a specific set of military objects (aircraft, car/truck, UAV, gunshots, tank). The result showed that the BEATS model with transformer finetuning layer demonstrated highest accuracy (93%). Confusion matrix analysis revealed that the models performed quite well in identifying the sounds of “UAV”, “car” and “gunshots”, but had difficulties in recognizing the sounds of “aircraft” and “tank”. The Beats model with the RNN-based modification showed better results in tank detection compared to other models, but had limited effectiveness in UAV detection. Overall, the results of our study confirm the promising use of modern SelfSL models for complex acoustic monitoring of military-significant objects and events. However, further research should be aimed at improving the reliability of detection of the classes “aircraft” and “tank”, which turned out to be the least effectively recognized categories for all considered models. Future work may include the development of new training methods, the use of larger and more diverse datasets, and the investigation of

the possibilities of multisensor integration to increase the overall reliability of acoustic monitoring systems.

Declaration on Generative AI The author(s) have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 42: Modeling of Transport Flows in Critical Situations

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Abstract: Cellular automata can be used to model traffic flow by applying a simple algorithm that regulates the acceleration and deceleration of vehicles. Despite its simplicity, this model allows for the observation of large-scale phenomena, such as traffic jams that propagate backward. These backward-propagating congestion patterns emerge naturally from the interactions between vehicles without the need for centralized control.

A variation of this model, implemented in MATLAB, was used to study how different parameters, such as vehicle density on the road or the number of lanes, affect traffic flow intensity. The simulation approach leverages a one-dimensional array of discrete cells, where each cell represents a possible vehicle position and its velocity.

Experiments revealed that in a system with a single lane and a maximum speed of 1, a phase transition occurs at a density of 0.08 cars per cell. This phase transition marks a critical shift in traffic dynamics: below the threshold, traffic flows freely, while above it, jams persist and propagate. Moreover, this transition was observed only in cases where the maximum speed exceeded one, confirming the non-linear nature of traffic flow dynamics even under simple rule sets.

Conclusions: The developed model demonstrated a fairly accurate representation of traffic flow. Simulations were performed for different numbers of lanes and vehicle densities, with initial car placements along the road being randomized. The movement of vehicles was dictated by a straightforward set of rules, which led to the emergence of complex behaviors such as traffic congestion.

For a single-lane road, a phase transition was observed at a density of 0.08 ± 0.01 cars per site. Beyond this point, any further increase in density resulted in a decline in the overall flow rate. The two-lane system exhibited a similar behavior, with a phase transition occurring around 0.20 ± 0.01 cars per site. As expected, the peak flow rate for the two-lane road was nearly double that of the single-lane case. The simulated flow rate versus density graph closely matched the patterns found in real traffic data. These two datasets, both simulated and real, were used to align arbitrary time steps and road

segment lengths with real-world metrics such as meters and seconds per hour. This allowed the model's outputs to be converted into practical, real-world traffic values.

At lower densities, the system reached a stable configuration where cars maintained even spacing with minimal interaction. However, as density increased, congestion became a dominant feature, with most vehicles being stuck in recurring traffic jams. These jams persisted as fundamental characteristics of the road, spreading in a backward direction.

For very high densities, the system either failed to reach a stable state or required an impractically long time to do so. To address this, simulations were conducted on extended road lengths ranging from 250 to 1000 units. However, these high-density configurations were not particularly useful for modeling, as vehicles spent most of their time in congestion. On the other hand, low-density scenarios were of greater interest, as they allowed for a more detailed examination of individual vehicle behavior.

Potential improvements to the model could include incorporating additional traffic control elements, such as traffic lights and intersections, to study their impact on traffic dynamics. Additionally, the current model lacks support for non-periodic roads without significant modifications to the distance calculation functions.

Moreover, the simulation highlighted the contrast between low- and high-density regimes. In low density conditions, vehicles tend to spread out, producing a steady-state configuration with little interaction. In contrast, at high densities, vehicles become locked in jams, leading to a breakdown of flow and persistent backward-propagating congestion waves. These jammed states rarely stabilized and often required road lengths of up to 1000 cells to observe significant trends.

While the current model effectively captures fundamental traffic behaviors, it can be further expanded. Future improvements may include support for non-periodic roads, simulation of dynamic elements such as traffic lights, roundabouts, or merging lanes, and integration with real geographic data using GIS. Additionally, incorporating driver variability, adaptive cruise control, or vehicle-to-vehicle communication could make the system more realistic. Such extensions would increase the model's applicability for urban planning, traffic optimization, and autonomous vehicle testing.

Article 43: Automatic Identification of Musical Instruments

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Abstract: This paper explores the application of the Fourier Transform for automatic musical instrument recognition in audio recordings. With the increasing complexity of musical compositions and the need for efficient audio classification, the study focuses on extracting detailed spectral features from sound signals using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). These features include spectral centroid, bandwidth, roll-off,

zero-crossing rate, and Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), which represent the frequency-based characteristics of different instruments. The extracted features are processed and used to train machine learning models. Specifically, the paper evaluates the performance of two classification algorithms: Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The models are trained on a dataset of short mono-instrument recordings and tested on mixed-instrument samples to assess generalization capabilities. The experimental results demonstrate that both models can effectively classify instruments with high accuracy—over 96% in controlled environments. However, the accuracy decreases in complex polyphonic recordings due to overlapping frequencies. The study also highlights the role of libraries such as Librosa, Numpy, and Scikit-learn for preprocessing and model training. The findings suggest that while the proposed approach is not ideal for overlapping instruments in orchestras, it is highly effective in solo instrument classification and can be extended to tasks like genre recognition. Future research could include deep learning techniques and sound source separation to improve performance in polyphonic settings.

Conclusions: The process of implementing and training the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models with the extracted spectral features was a crucial step in evaluating the potential of machine learning for musical instrument classification. Upon evaluation, both models exhibited high accuracy in controlled conditions, where the audio recordings had minimal overlapping sounds from multiple instruments and were of relatively short duration. This finding highlights the effectiveness of the approach when the data is well-suited to the model's capabilities.

In controlled settings, the spectral features extracted from the audio—such as the Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs), spectral centroid, and spectral flux—proved to be reliable indicators for distinguishing between different musical instruments. The training process was efficient, and both ANN and SVM models showed promising results, accurately classifying single-instrument recordings.

However, when transitioning from controlled environments to more complex, real-world orchestra recordings, where multiple instruments often overlap, the models faced significant challenges. The spectral features, although still informative, struggled to differentiate between instruments when their sounds merged within the same frequency ranges. This limitation underscores the inherent difficulty of handling polyphonic audio, where multiple sound sources are present simultaneously. While both models still performed reasonably well under these conditions, their accuracy and robustness were noticeably affected.

Despite these challenges, the approach remains valuable for audio classification tasks, particularly in simpler cases such as genre classification or identifying solo instruments. In these applications, spectral features effectively capture the distinct characteristics of different sounds, and the models can be trained to classify them with high accuracy. The simplicity of the method, combined with its effectiveness under

controlled conditions, makes it an accessible tool for various audio analysis applications.

In conclusion, the application of spectral analysis in conjunction with machine learning algorithms like ANN and SVM provides a solid foundation for music-related classification tasks. The current approach shows great promise for controlled settings but requires further refinement to handle complex polyphonic and overlapping audio scenarios effectively. Future work should focus on improving the models' ability to handle multiple instruments simultaneously, potentially incorporating advanced techniques such as source separation or deep learning methods specifically designed for polyphonic sound analysis.

Article 44: The Impact of Game-Based Environments on Spatial Thinking: Investigating the Potential Influence

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Abstract: In the modern world, gaming environments play a crucial role not only as a form of entertainment but also as a tool for skill development. Spatial thinking is a fundamental cognitive ability that affects various aspects of life, from everyday navigation to professional fields such as architecture, engineering, and design. Despite its importance, there is still a limited understanding of how interactive 3D environments, including video games and virtual reality applications, contribute to the development of spatial skills. This paper explores the relationship between gaming technologies and spatial cognition, emphasizing both the potential benefits and challenges. Research suggests that engaging with 3D puzzles and virtual environments can improve mental rotation, spatial visualization, and problem-solving skills. While early childhood development is particularly influenced by spatial reasoning activities, adults can also enhance their spatial abilities through targeted training. The study highlights real-world applications, from improved map navigation and object manipulation to increased efficiency in STEM-related tasks. Further investigation is required to optimize game design for cognitive training and to identify best practices for integrating spatial learning into interactive digital experiences.

Conclusions: We have taken a fascinating journey in research, demonstrating how interactive 3D applications can be effective tools for shaping spatial thinking and representation. Through the use of mazes, puzzles, and dynamic environments, users not only enjoy the gameplay, but also subconsciously develop important cognitive skills that are practical in everyday life. Our vision of the future includes interactive technologies that actively foster the kind of thinking required of engineers, mathematicians, and scientists. This perspective opens up new horizons: from optimizing design skills to facilitating the learning of complex spatial concepts. However, this area remains open for further research and improvements, including: • Expanding the functionality of interactive environments: Adding new levels of

complexity, various tasks, and personalization options to meet user needs. • Adaptation to professional training: Development of specialized scenarios for architects, engineers, and designers that simulate real professional challenges. • Individualized learning: Utilizing adaptive learning algorithms that adjust to the individual progress of users, facilitating more effective development of spatial skills. • Integration with VR/AR: Leveraging virtual and augmented reality to create even more realistic and immersive learning experiences. Interactive 3D environments are already changing the approach to learning by combining technology and human potential. In the future, they can become a powerful tool for developing critical skills needed to solve complex analytical and creative problems. Let's open up new opportunities together by embracing the challenges of our time and using technology to push the boundaries of our thinking.

Article 45: Modal Systems with Separate Dominance of Experts in Logics of Partial Predicates

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Abstract: Modal logics, particularly temporal and epistemic, are widely and successfully applied in modern information and software systems, artificial intelligence systems, knowledge bases and expert systems. This paper investigates special modal logics of the epistemic type, based on first-order logics of partial quasiary predicates. At the core of the studied logics lies the concept of a multiple-expert modal system (MEMS). To describe such systems, we use semantic models of the relational type. The presence of multiple experts in a system implies that each of them may hold a distinct opinion about a given situation, which complicates the process of reaching a final decision. To coordinate decisions, a dominance relation is introduced on the set of experts. In known multiple-expert systems, dominance typically requires the preservation of true: if a dominant expert considers a statement to be true, the subdominant expert must also consider it true. We propose modal systems based on logics of partial single-valued predicates, where it is more appropriate to preserve the truth value of statements under dominance: both true and false must be preserved, not only true. However, this may lead to inconsistency in situations where expert e is directly dominated by two experts, a and b , such that a considers a statement Q to be true, while b considers Q to be false. To avoid such issues, we propose introducing a separate dominance relation on a set of experts – meaning that no expert can be directly dominated by more than one other expert. In this work, we describe the language of pure first-order MEMS, provide a formal definition of formulas in the language, and specify the interpretation mapping for formulas on semantic models. Special attention is given to the features of the relation of separate dominance. We formulate conditions for truth-value preservation of atomic formulas under dominance and prove that these conditions can be extended to all formulas of the language. In future work, we plan to

explore logical consequence relations in MEMS languages and develop sequent-type calculi for MEMS. We also aim to generalize MEMS to the case of logics of ambiguous (non-deterministic) predicates, which would allow us to lift the requirement of separate dominance.

Conclusions: This paper studies special modal logics of the epistemic type, which are based on pure first-order logics of partial quasiary predicates. At the foundation of the investigated logics lies the concept of a multiple-expert modal system (MEMS). We propose modal systems with a relation of separate dominance defined on a set of experts. This means that no expert can be directly dominated by more than one other expert. Unlike known similar systems, our approach requires that both true and false values are preserved under dominance, not only true. Such separateness of dominance makes it possible to avoid incorrect situations. The paper describes the language of pure first-order MEMS, provides definitions of formulas of the language, and determines the interpretation mapping of formulas on semantic models. Special attention is given to the features of the separate dominance relation. Conditions for truth value preservation under dominance are formulated for atomic formulas and proven to extend to all formulas of the language. Further research on MEMS can be pursued in several directions: generalizing MEMS to the case of logics of ambiguous (non-deterministic) predicates; studying MEMS with various properties of dominance and accessibility relations; defining and investigating logical consequence relations in the MEMS languages; and developing sequent-type calculi for MEMS. We plan to address these directions in future work.

Declaration on Generative AI The authors have not employed any Generative AI tools.

Article 46: Extreme Values of a Global Minimum Cut in Connected Regular Graphs

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Abstract: Strict lower and upper bounds on the size of a global minimum cut in connected regular graphs are presented. Examples of graphs achieving equality in either bound are presented. Graphs achieving equality in the lower bound are exhaustively enumerated. A stronger conjecture is presented for a subclass of circulant graphs. It is experimentally verified for a large number of small circulants. Connected regular graphs play an important role in network design. Global minimum cut is a key numerical characteristic of robust connectivity. Circulant graphs are a frequent choice of network topology in practical applications.

Conclusions: In this paper, we established upper and lower bounds on the edge connectivity of connected regular graphs. We illustrated that our bounds are tight with a variety of examples. For the lower bound, we additionally enumerated all graphs that

achieve it. This is done via the enumeration of both subgraphs induced by the minimum cut.

One practical application of this enumeration is that one may construct a database of poorly connected subgraph and their hashes. It allows us to quickly check if a certain subgraph is poorly connected. The downside of this approach is that a subgraph must be regular, which is often not the case even if the overall graph is regular.

Further practical significance of our findings is that we can now derive an approximation algorithm for the task of adding a small number of edges to a given graph in a way that maximizes edge connectivity.

The algorithm will enumerate all poorly connected subgraphs and sequentially augment them with missing edges that increase edge connectivity. Since a given edge can only belong to a limited number of subgraphs, our algorithm is a true approximation, not a heuristic. Naturally, any practical polynomial-time algorithm must find candidate subgraphs more efficiently.

Since we enumerated all poorly connected regular graphs, one may also utilize that characterization with a different refinement step that may yield better results. Examples include fewer added edges to reach the target edge connectivity or a higher edge connectivity reached within a given budget (number of edges that can be added).

Article 47: Sensor-Driven Artificial Lighting Analysis in Buildings Using IOT and AI

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Abstract: This paper presents the development and implementation of a portable IoT-based sensor system for monitoring artificial lighting conditions in indoor environments, enhanced by advanced AI-driven data analysis capabilities. The main objective is to create an autonomous measurement platform capable of collecting, analyzing, and transmitting lighting flow data using modern microcontroller, cloud technologies, and artificial intelligence models for comprehensive data interpretation. The ESP32 Luanode32 microcontroller was equipped with three specialized sensors: a BH1750 light intensity sensor for luminosity measurements, an ADPS9960 proximity and gesture sensor for environmental interaction detection, and a DHT22 sensor for temperature and humidity monitoring to provide comprehensive environmental context. Power management was addressed through the implementation of a 6000mAh lithium polymer battery system equipped with integrated charge and discharge control circuits. DC-DC voltage converters were incorporated to ensure a stable power supply distribution across all system components. The system architecture incorporates both

local data processing capabilities within the microcontroller and cloud-based analysis through the Thingspeak platform for remote monitoring and data visualization. Advanced artificial intelligence analysis was implemented using Claude Sonnet 4 and Gemini 2.5 Pro language models to process and interpret the collected sensor data. These AI systems were employed for pattern recognition in lighting usage behaviors, correlation analysis between environmental parameters and lighting efficiency, and generation of automated insights regarding optimal lighting conditions. The AI models processed historical data trends to identify anomalies in lighting patterns and provided predictive analytics for energy consumption optimization. Initial testing demonstrated successful data collection and transmission capabilities, with the module effectively measuring artificial lighting parameters while maintaining stable operation through the integrated power management system. The AI-enhanced analysis revealed previously undetected patterns in lighting usage, with Claude Sonnet 4 providing detailed contextual interpretations of sensor data relationships and Gemini 2.5 Pro contributing advanced statistical analysis of environmental correlations. The prototype successfully established reliable communication with the Thingspeak cloud platform, enabling real-time data monitoring, AI-powered analysis, and automated report generation.

Conclusions: The analysis of BH1750 and APDS9960 sensor data revealed a sophisticated and dynamic lighting environment. The observed fluctuations in lux levels and the concurrent shifts in RGB ratios strongly suggest the presence of tunable LED lighting or a combination of different artificial light sources. This illuminance and color temperature adaptability indicates an active implementation of Human-Centric Lighting principles, aiming to enhance occupant well-being and productivity. However, a significant concern arises from the detection of extreme light pulsation, or flicker, which represents a critical degradation in lighting quality. While the system demonstrates advanced adaptive control and color tuning capabilities, the flicker issue undermines these benefits and warrants immediate attention. The current system demonstrates a foundation for intelligent lighting, and further enhancements can propel it towards a more advanced and responsive environment. Leverage the rich sensor data to develop or refine AI and machine learning models. These models can be trained to learn user preferences, predict optimal lighting conditions based on various inputs (time of day, weather forecasts, occupancy patterns), and proactively detect anomalies or maintenance needs. This progression moves the system towards truly intelligent and autonomous building automation, where lighting adapts seamlessly without manual intervention. Advanced sensor deployment integration and additional sensor types can be added to provide more granular and comprehensive data. This could include dedicated occupancy sensors for precise presence detection, voice sensors for intuitive control, or more advanced spectral sensors for accurate Color Rendering Index (CRI) measurements. Richer data enables more nuanced and effective adaptive lighting, allowing for personalization based on individual user biometric data or real-time activity. Furthermore, ensuring seamless interoperability between different

manufacturers' devices and communication protocols (Zigbee, Bluetooth Mesh, LoRaWAN) will prevent fragmentation and ensure long-term system flexibility and scalability. Proactive attention to these areas is crucial for maintaining system reliability and user trust in an increasingly interconnected smart environment.

Declaration on Generative AI During the preparation of this work, the authors used Claude Sonnet 4, Gemini 2.5 Pro, DeepL Translate, and Grammarly in order to: grammar and spelling check, improve writing style, and manage citations. After using these services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the publication's content.

Article 48: On the Construction of Stable Matchings in the Algorithm for the Optimal Testing Problem

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Abstract: This article addresses a problem at the intersection of two optimization challenges: stable matching of pairs and minimizing the total cost of binary tests. Stable matching ensures equilibrium in systems where agents or resources need to be paired, while cost minimization reduces inefficiencies and resource waste. By combining these perspectives, we construct an approach balancing stability with optimal cost management. We developed a simple matching algorithm that effectively solves this problem. The algorithm is rigorously proven to be optimal both in minimizing total testing costs and maintaining stability in pairwise matching. Additionally, it ensures alignment between global optimization goals and individual agent incentives, eliminating inefficiencies caused by the “price of anarchy.” In this way, agents acting selfishly do not harm overall system performance, making the algorithm suitable for decentralized and multi-agent systems. The algorithm's effectiveness is demonstrated through mathematical modeling and simulations, showing robustness across varying agent quality distributions and test costs. Its simplicity and computational efficiency make it practical for real-world applications such as resource allocation, automated decision making, and optimization tasks requiring agent or resource pairings. This work contributes to optimization research by providing a versatile and efficient solution to the combined problem of stable matching and cost minimization. Future studies could extend its use to dynamic systems or multi-objective optimization tasks, solidifying its role as a practical tool for modern information systems and resource management challenges.

Conclusions: The constructed matching algorithm presented in this article establishes a significant advancement in solving optimization problems involving pairwise matching. By combining mathematical rigor with practical simplicity, the algorithm offers a universal solution that can be applied across a wide range of domains. The core contributions and findings of this work can be summarized as follows: 1.

Optimality and Theoretical Foundations: the proposed algorithm is mathematically proven to produce the optimal matching for resource allocation and pairing problems. This guarantees that its solutions represent the best possible outcomes under the given constraints, ensuring its reliability and robustness. 2. Simplicity of Implementation: the algorithm's implementation relies on basic computational steps, such as array sorting, making it lightweight, efficient, and accessible. This simplicity makes the algorithm practical for immediate integration into existing systems without requiring substantial computational resources or complex infrastructure. 3. Alignment of Individual and Global Optima: one of the most remarkable properties of the algorithm is its inherent harmony between individual self-interest and total system optimization. The absence of the "price of anarchy" demonstrates that the algorithms' solutions equally benefit all participating agents while aligning with overall system goals. This property makes it especially valuable for decentralized systems and multi-agent environments where conflicts between individual and collective objectives frequently occur. 4. Quantitative Evaluation through Simulation: the algorithm's performance can be quantitatively evaluated through simulations under various scenarios and stochastic conditions. This capability not only validates its effectiveness but also provides insights into its potential outcomes in real-world applications, offering flexibility and reliability in applications involving uncertain or dynamic conditions. 5. Versatility and Applicability: the algorithm has broad applications across various domains, including energy resource optimization, task allocation in distributed systems, logistics and supply chain management, cloud computing, and network optimization. Its scalability allows it to solve problems in environments with large datasets or decentralized autonomy, making it a powerful tool for modern information systems and operational challenges. In conclusion, the matching algorithm constructed in this work represents a rare combination of theoretical rigor, practical simplicity, and universal applicability. By resolving complex pairwise optimization problems with minimal computational overhead and proving its effectiveness mathematically, the algorithm sets a strong foundation for further research and real-world applications. Future work could explore its adaptation to dynamic systems with evolving agent characteristics or extend its principles to more complex multi-agent and multi-objective scenarios, further unlocking its potential in addressing modern challenges in optimization and resource allocation.

Article 49: Synchronization of Two Coupled Nonlinear Dynamical Systems

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Abstract: The paper deals with designing a theoretical framework to study and construct control systems for coupled dynamical subsystems. The design of the above-mentioned framework is based on the analysis of coupled systems’ motions and using these motions to define the trajectories of system-perturbed motions. System motions are considered in both continuous-time and discrete-time domains in the most general case for the nonlinear system and we propose the algorithm to define such system’s perturbed motion equations. Due to the system’s nonlinearities the exact analytical definition of the perturbed motion is hard enough that is why the use of interval methods is suggested and considered of system dynamic in piecewise linear form is offered. Such an approach allows us to define system perturbed motion equations in an easy way. These equations are used to design a controller to synchronize both subsystems’ motions. Our research shows the possibility of designing both a master-slave control system and a dual-channel one to perform such synchronization. The use of the proposed approach is proven by simulation results of a Duffing pendulum with driven exciter which one can use as the basis to implement a control system and synchronize to subsystems.

Conclusions: Performed studies prove the possibility of using interval methods to study and design closed-loop control systems to synchronize various parts of coupled systems. Such a synchronization twice reduce coupled system order and according to Poincare theorem about chaotic motions makes system motions regular. Designed in such a way control systems can be considered as discontinuous control systems with variable minimal and maximal values of produced control signals. One can define the control signal boundaries by taking into account the system perturbed motion equation and solving on its basis the inverse dynamic problem. Such a solution has some general patterns which allow to simplify the control signal determination. We see the future development of our work in applying our approach to high-order chaotic systems for designing based on the second-order sliding mode approach continuous and discrete control systems to perform its synchronization and setup secured data transmission channels in environment with interconnected transmitter and receiver.

Article 50: Software-Based Modeling and Performance Analysis of Hybrid IoT Networks for Agricultural Monitoring

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Abstract: Current precision farming practices have become more technology- and data-driven, so the need for robust, adaptive, and flexible software-driven info-

communication networks becomes essential. This article presents a hybrid IoT network model designed for agro-monitoring, integrating multiple wireless technologies such as 5G, LTE, Wi-Fi, and Zigbee. The simulation aims to analyze the interactions between these technologies and evaluate their performance in different agricultural scenarios. Key metrics include data transmission speed, latency, energy efficiency, and network resilience under varying conditions. The findings demonstrate the advantages of a hybrid approach, particularly in enhancing connectivity and ensuring efficient data flow in complex agricultural environments. The proposed approach is based on a software platform designed to optimize the integration and performance of hybrid IoT networks, addressing challenges in real-time agricultural monitoring.

Conclusions: The study demonstrates that hybrid networks are a promising solution for addressing the communication needs of agro-monitoring systems. By integrating multiple wireless technologies such as 5G, LTE, Wi-Fi, and Zigbee, it is possible to optimize network performance across various agricultural environments. The simulation results provide both quantitative and qualitative insights into the effectiveness of these technologies in enhancing agricultural productivity. The key findings of this article are as follows: 1. The simulation revealed that 5G provided a maximum data transmission speed of 1.5 Gbps, significantly outperforming LTE's 150 Mbps and Wi-Fi's 30 Mbps. Zigbee, while lower in speed at 20 Kbps, excels in low-energy consumption, consuming only 0.05 W per device. This highlights the trade off between speed and energy efficiency in selecting appropriate technologies for specific applications. 2. The study measured latency across the network, with 5G exhibiting the lowest latency at 10 ms, compared to LTE's 30 ms and Zigbee's 50 ms. This underscores 5G's suitability for real-time applications in agriculture, such as autonomous vehicle control and drone monitoring. 3. The hybrid network showed a significant reduction in overall energy consumption when utilizing Zigbee for sensor networks. The combination of Zigbee with high-speed technologies like 5G allows for efficient data transmission without draining battery resources, extending device lifespan. The key recommendations are as follows: Invest in 5G infrastructure where feasible, focusing on regions with high agricultural output to benefit from real-time data monitoring and control. The results suggest that enhanced infrastructure can directly impact data collection efficiency and operational effectiveness. 4. Implement a multi-tier network approach, where each technology plays a role based on specific requirements, such as coverage, speed, or energy efficiency. The findings indicate that this tailored approach can maximize the advantages of each technology. 5. Prioritize the use of low-power technologies like Zigbee for sensor networks to enhance battery life and reduce operational costs. The energy consumption analysis supports this recommendation by showing significant savings when employing Zigbee in hybrid networks. 6. Design the network with scalability in mind, allowing for easy expansion or modification as agricultural technology continues to evolve. The study's results advocate for a flexible network that can adapt to changing agricultural demands. In

conclusion, the hybrid network approach offers significant advantages in terms of connectivity, data transmission, and energy efficiency, making it a viable solution for enhancing agricultural productivity and sustainability. Future research could focus on refining the integration process between these technologies, particularly in scenarios where rapid scaling is required. By continually evaluating and optimizing the performance of hybrid networks, agriculture can benefit from enhanced monitoring systems that support smarter, more efficient farming practices.